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International Journal of Science Annals

EDITORIAL

EDITORIAL

Using of ChatGPT in Psychology Research and Practice

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- A – Study design;
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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

The use of artificial intelligence-based (AI-based) Chatbots in scientific research and everyday practice is becoming an integral part of most people's lives. The field of psychology, like many others, has been influenced by artificial intelligence (AI).

The aim of the study: to explore the possibilities of using AI-based Chatbots in psychological research and practice.

Results:

The role of OpenAI's ChatGPT in the scientific research of academics and psychology practitioners was reviewed. The issues of using ChatGPT, which specializes in text, in theoretical research were discussed, as well as the potential applications of AI-based Chatbots in psychological practice.

Conclusions:

New AI technologies have transformed the scientific research ecosystem. Researchers, who actively use ChatGPT, should do so properly, taking into account the possibilities and limitations of using this toolkit in their research. Borrowing an AI-generated text for a research paper should be considered plagiarism. In addition to the risk to professional reputation, this can have a negative impact on the researcher's own personal progress. People who do not have access to a qualified professional or who are financially constrained can use ChatGPT in psychological practice. In one way or another, these users must realize that the responsibility for the results and consequences of using such a toolkit rests entirely with them.

Keywords:

ChatGPT, artificial intelligence, psychology research, psychology practice, possibilities, responsibility

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Introduction

Dozens of artificial intelligence-based (AI-based) tools with different specializations for text, photo, video, etc. are being created every day. AI-based Chatbots are becoming more advanced and their use is growing rapidly.

Of particular note is OpenAI's ChatGPT, which specializes in text (Large Language Models) and is the most developed and popular among users today. In the first two months of OpenAI's ChatGPT, more than 100 million people became its active users. According to

Reuters (Hu, 2023), the analysts note that in the last 20 years in the Internet space, it is hard to remember a faster growth rate for consumer Internet applications.

Results

Let us consider the possibilities of using ChatGPT in scientific and practical spheres of psychologists' activity. Note that if we were asked the specific direct question of whether ChatGPT could replace the work of a psychologist, we would answer "no". ChatGPT or similar chat tools that may be created in the future are not capable of replacing the work of a "live" psychologist. This applies to both scientific and practical areas. Although ChatGPT or other AI tools can be used in academic and practitioner settings and positively impact the effectiveness of that work. However, they cannot adequately replace a live expert in the field.

Let us consider some arguments that we believe strengthen this position.

First, we discuss **using ChatGPT for psychological research.**

When studying any psychological phenomenon or writing research papers, we face the problem of reviewing a large number of references. Today, it is actually unnecessary to visit libraries, as most books are digitized and modern academic periodicals are available on the Internet (in scientometric databases, repositories and search engines). ChatGPT certainly has access to a lot of this information. Sometimes we do not even realize it. ChatGPT is also capable of self-selecting relevant literature, reviewing it, and drawing conclusions from it. This is a great temptation for the researcher working under time constraints.

In this way, young researchers had free and unrestricted access to information without having to analyze it independently. We did not have that in the not-so-distant past – when we had to spend all day in libraries, searching catalogs for the books we needed, ordering them one by one, and writing citations for our dissertations.

However, the benefits that ChatBots give us at first glance come at a price. A researcher who receives a "ready-made conclusion", even if ChatGPT has described the algorithm step by step, deprives himself of the opportunity to touch the primary sources and realize the essence for the formation of certain ideas, psychological concepts, theories and practices. In this way, the researcher saves time on the one hand, but on the other hand deprives himself of the opportunity to develop intellectually by relying entirely on ChatBots for the validity of the literature analysis and the conclusions drawn from it. It is quite possible that such actions could jeopardize his professional reputation and certainly will not contribute to his personal growth.

We emphasize that borrowing other people's ideas is an unacceptable practice that can be equated to plagiarism. Even if these ideas or conclusions are generated by artificial intelligence (AI).

In general, compliance with ethical principles and standards of academic integrity is an important aspect that may be underestimated, consciously or unconsciously, by a researcher using Chatbots.

It is important to note the statement of the Committee of Publication Ethics (COPE). On its website, the Committee has published its official position on authorship and the use of AI tools (COPE Council, 2021; COPE, 30 January 2023, 13 February 2023, 23 February 2023; Watson & Stiglic, 2023). Also a number of papers on using AI for scientific writing (Çalli & Çalli, 2022; Dans, 2019; Dimitriadou & Lanitis, 2023; Farahani, 2023; Singh & Sood, 2022).

The IJSA is a full member of the COPE (COPE, n.d.). The Editorial Board recommends that researchers take the issue of quality and use of AI in manuscript writing and text citation seriously (Melnyk & Pypenko, 2021, 2023). Especially since there will soon be programs that can determine the extent to which AI-based ChatBots are involved in writing a research paper.

The development of programs capable of recognizing machine-generated text is evidenced by the statement of researcher Scott Aaronson of the OpenAI Company (Hern, 2022). Turnitin has already begun work on developing an AI-based text detection tool (Chechitelli, 2023). So there is a good chance that if you try to pretend to be the author of text written by a ChatBot, you may be detected.

Emphasize that the above was an inappropriate borrowing of ideas and text written by ChatGPT. This does not mean at all that we are strongly against the use of ChatGPT. On the contrary, the use of ChatGPT or other AI tools in a research paper is a sign that the researcher is able to use modern methods and tools correctly.

To conclude the discussion of the use of ChatGPT in psychological research, I would like to make one more argument related to the inability of AI to replace the work of a research psychologist.

We have a reasonable belief that AI or the latest modification of ChatGPT will not be able to develop a fundamentally new psychological approach or theory. This is because ChatGPT's possibilities will always be conditioned and connected to the human ability to ask questions.

At this stage of AI development, it is hard to see how ChatGPT, for example, could develop and describe something like a psychoanalytic approach, or how ChatGPT could conduct psychoanalytic sessions with humans. Despite the fact that most clients still naively believe that this is a fairly simple method of formulating questions with fairly limited involvement of the psychoanalyst.

Second, we discuss **using ChatGPT for psychological practice.**

Most people evaluate AI, like any digital product (Pypenko, 2019), from the consumer's point of view. For some people, technological innovation provokes technophobia, in some cases even paranoia. This has only gotten worse with the advent of AI and Chatbots. Such people tend to view ChatBot as an evil agent spawned by computers and the Internet. In addition, there are a growing number of people with the exact opposite condition – nomophobia, which is related to the fear and despair of being disconnected from technological

devices. These people prefer communicating with gadgets to real human interaction. They become so addicted to ChatBots that they turn to them for everything. For example, what to talk about with your partner or what to discuss with your manager and what to avoid, what text to use in a personal message or an official document, etc.

We believe that ChatGPT technology will improve with each passing year. Given today's realities, we can expect the need for human communication with others to steadily decrease.

However, no matter how much the developers improve ChatGPT, it will never become the owner of a human soul.

In this context, it is appropriate to recall Carl Jung's position. Over a hundred years ago, he pointed out the importance of learning theories and techniques, but these should be set aside when touching the miracle of the living soul (Jung, 1928).

Psychology is a special field of human activity that deals with the human soul. Even if the psychologist uses certain tools and technologies, it is still communication that takes place in a person-to-person system.

Today we can see the emergence of a new system – the "Human-AI System". This term was suggested by Melnyk and Pypenko (2023). Human-AI System is a complicated dynamic complex of interactions between living and non-living matter, is an accumulation of coordinated, interdependent and interconnected informational-technological actions of human and AI, oriented to learn from the information obtained, designed to effectively perform tasks and achieve goals (Melnyk & Pypenko, 2023, p. 7).

The views expressed in this Editorial are based on more than twenty years of experience in studying the use of psychotechnology. In 2002 I justified and introduced the term "psychotechnologies" into the scientific circulation, developed and began to teach the author's course "Fundamentals of Psychotechnologies" at the National Pedagogical University (Melnyk, 2011). I have also had extensive practice in public schools, high schools, and universities working with children and adolescents, as well as a private counseling practice for adults.

Whenever I started to tell students about this or that psychological approach, theory, technique, and method, I always tried to convey to them the main idea – the indispensable role of the psychotherapeutic relationship between therapist and client. In this sense, Irvin Yalom's words, "It's the relationship that heals" (Yalom, 2012, p.112), can be considered prophetic.

Today, few would argue that computerized testing and the resulting recommendations can be as effective as direct communication with a "live" psychologist.

However, such areas of activity of a practical psychologist as counseling, correctional-developmental, psychoprophylactic work should be carried out directly with personal contact.

The resurgence of client requests for face-to-face counseling after the lifting of the COVID restrictions that caused psychologists to switch to online counseling will be an additional argument.

Conclusions

We are in the early stages of learning about the new Human-AI System. The dual position, which divides everything into opposite sides (good and evil), is untenable in the issue of confronting AI and the psychologist's activity. The possibilities of ChatGPT, like other Chatbots, are conditioned and dependent on the human ability to ask questions. The transition of the new neural networks to dialog mode has allowed ChatGPT to become an effective tool for scientists and interesting for a wide range of users. ChatGPT, like any other AI-based Chatbot, is not capable of replacing a real psychologist. It should be considered a valuable resource for information handling, call analysis, scheduling, and in some other cases.

Humanity should learn to harness the potential of AI for the common good, both for people and for the development of new technologies. At the same time, the questions of responsibility and ethics of these relationships should become issues of principle. This will enable the harmonious coexistence and sustainable development of psychological theory and practice in the future.

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**SOCIAL AND
BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES**

Education

SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES. Education

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Prediction of Arithmetic Abilities of Children Who Practice Sports: The Use of the Gamma Model

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
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- F – Literature search;
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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

The physical performance that children exhibit when engaging in sports or any form of physical activity will depend not only on their physical abilities but also on their psychological and cognitive attributes.

The aim of the study: to analyze whether symptoms of anxiety, lie, attention, and age are predictors of arithmetic abilities in children practicing sports.

Material and Methods:

The study sample consisted of 108 children with an average age of 12.12 (± 2.18) who practice various sports, with greater emphasis on futsal and soccer. The study protocol consisted of a sociodemographic questionnaire, the Revised Children's Manifest Anxiety Scale, the d2 Test of Attention, and the Arithmetic subtest of the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children.

Results:

The results showed that through the adjusted model, we identify four significant explanatory variables that are predictors of arithmetic abilities, namely anxiety symptoms ($\beta = -0.009$, $p = 0.009$); and the attention sub-factors: processed characters ($\beta = 0.002$, $p = 3.44e-14$), default errors ($\beta = -0.005$, $p = 0.000$), errors by marking irrelevant characters ($\beta = -0.016$, $p = 0.003$).

Conclusions:

The presence of anxiety symptoms and attentional cognitive abilities play a significant role in predicting the arithmetic aptitudes of young individuals. These variables should be taken into consideration within training programs for young athletes, as they hold relevance for sports engagement.

Keywords:

sports participants, anxiety, lie, attention, age, arithmetic skills

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Introduction

Physical activity and sports hold a pivotal role in the promotion of health and overall well-being. The engagement of young individuals in physical activities and sports has been correlated with favorable impacts on their mental health, encompassing emotional states, behavioral patterns, and cognitive proficiencies (Hosker et al., 2019). The cultivation of cognitive capacities, particularly arithmetic abilities, equips children and adolescents with enhanced precision in numerical comprehension, mathematical operations, point enumeration, and improved numerical estimations, among other competencies (Landerl, 2013; Reeve et al., 2012). These proficiencies are notably nurtured through participation in games (Butterworth, 2005). The refinement of such abilities necessitates the establishment of neural connections, exemplified by linkages between visual and verbal networks, as well as visual and spatial networks (Rapin, 2016), both of which hold equal significance in the context of sports performance (Tamorri, 2004). Moreover, a discernible correlation has been substantiated between arithmetic skills and self-reported levels of physical activity, aerobic fitness, and motor prowess (Syväoja et al., 2021). Notably, motor skills have been identified as integral to fundamental numerical abilities, encompassing aspects such as symbolic representation on the number line (number identification) and nonsymbolic representation (object identification) (Gashaj et al., 2019a). The predictive linkage between fine motor skills and arithmetic competencies is also highlighted in a study conducted by Michel et al. (2020) involving 173 children. The utilization of gestures or manual manipulations has been shown to confer benefits in the accuracy and swiftness of item counting (Carlson et al., 2007). The presence of proficient fine motor skills additionally emerges as a predictor for mathematical prowess among children aged 7 to 8 years, as evidenced by Gashaj et al. (2019b). In light of these insights, it becomes apparent that sports training and the augmentation of motor capabilities exert tangible effects upon the arithmetic aptitudes of children who are engaged in sports activities. Moreover, in accordance with the investigation conducted by Wu et al. (2017), cognitive faculties encompassing working memory and attention, alongside affective constituents such as mathematical anxiety, emerge as pivotal contributors to mathematical performance across both verbal and non-verbal tasks. Nevertheless, the presence of mathematical anxiety has been shown to impede the cognitive processes essential to proficient task execution within this domain (Orbach et al., 2020). Mathematical anxiety constitutes an adverse emotional response characterized by feelings of unease and apprehension that students experience when confronted with mathematical exercises (Hill et al., 2016), and this phenomenon can exert a detrimental influence on their mathematical comprehension and problem-solving skills (Vukovic et al., 2013). Such anxiety can instigate intrusive negative thoughts and engender a perception of environmental stimuli as threatening. Consequently, instances of math

anxiety within children can elicit avoidance behaviors when confronted with arithmetic challenges (Orbach et al., 2020). Consequently, it is hypothesized that the presence of anxiety may disrupt the arithmetic proficiencies of the participants under examination. However, an alternative perspective posited by Wu et al. (2017) contends that when mathematical anxiety prevails, there might be an elevation in children's levels of vigilance, potentially serving as a mitigating factor against the adverse impact of attentional deficits on mathematical performance. Steele et al. (2012) study, analyzing the developmental trajectory of children's attentional capacities, identified sustained-selective attention as a predictive indicator of fundamental mathematical abilities over a one-year observation period. Evidently, tasks involving counting necessitate the engagement of serial attentional processes. In these contexts, discrepancies in attentional proficiency may contribute to disparities in children's performance concerning mathematical problem-solving (Wu et al., 2017). The mechanism of attention entails focusing on stimuli of significance, thereby sieving a substantial portion of sensory input and directing cognitive processing toward selected components (Broadbent, 1958; Deutsch & Deutsch, 1963). Within the realm of sports, attention assumes a pivotal function for athletes in identifying, selecting, or quantifying pertinent stimuli during both training sessions and competitive events (Carrascosa, 2003). This perspective prompts us to contemplate the possibility of attention serving as a predictive determinant of arithmetic proficiencies among children engaged in sports. Nevertheless, instances may arise wherein children, when grappling with task challenges, resort to deception. This utilization of deceit can manifest as a coping mechanism for evading tasks, concealing uncertainties, and masking weaknesses (Matias et al., 2015). Children frequently deploy falsehoods as a means of navigating their recreational pursuits. In the sporting context, the dissemination of false information can also be construed as an intentional strategic maneuver that disadvantages adversaries and strategically shapes opponents' behavior (Sailors et al., 2017). According to Ommundsen et al. (2003), children undergoing training to enhance soccer performance often exhibit heightened tendencies towards amoral conduct compared to their peers demonstrating elevated sociomoral maturity and adherence to fair-play principles. The conceptual framework advanced by Bransford and Stein (1993) frames lying as a form of decision-making employed when resolving problems risks compromising achievement objectives. As children mature, their cognitive capacities for fabricating falsehoods improve (Evans & Lee, 2011), thereby signifying that older children tend to wield lies more adeptly (Maggioni & Rossignoli, 2020). In this vein, it is posited that age and the engagement in deceit could potentially exert influence over the arithmetic abilities of children. Nonetheless, the intricacies of these abilities continue to command substantial scholarly attention. Scientific inquiry has delved into the associations between

arithmetic skills and various cognitive constructs, including working memory, executive functions (Orbach et al., 2020; Swanson & Beebe-Frankenberger, 2004), interactivity, mathematical anxiety (Vallée-Tourangeau, 2013), performance (Salminen et al., 2018), and even finger-counting practices (Barrocas et al., 2020; Crollen & Noël, 2015). While Becker et al. (2018) have demonstrated a correlation between engagement in team sports and enhanced mathematical problem-solving abilities, studies investigating the interplay of attention, anxiety, deception, and age in the mathematical capacities of children and adolescents active in sports are conspicuously scarce.

The aim of the study. To examine how symptoms of anxiety, lying, attention, and age are predictors of mathematical abilities in children who practice sports.

Materials and Methods

Participants

This observational, cross-sectional study, based on a non-probabilistic sample, considered 108 Portuguese participants with a mean age of 12.12 years (± 2.18), ranging from a minimum of 8 years to a maximum of 16 years. Most participants are male 66.7% and have completed the 3rd cycle of education (9 years of education) (43.5%). The most popular sports in the sample are futsal (37.0%), football (25.0%), taekwondo (17.6%), rhythmic gymnastics (7.4%), and tennis (7.4%). Participants have been practicing sports, on average, for 54.85 (± 28.68) months and the average weekly training time is 3.97 hours (± 2.6). As inclusion criteria, young athletes from sports clubs for at least one year were considered. Participation in the study was only accepted after signing the informed consent of the young person and their legal representative. They were informed that their participation was completely voluntary and harmless. Young people with developmental disorders or other physical and mental conditions that did not allow them to respond to the study protocol were not considered in this study. All ethical and deontological duties inherent to the investigation were considered.

Measures

For the present investigation, a sociodemographic questionnaire was used to collect information about the participants (e.g., age, sex, time of the sport, etc.). The Revised Children's Manifest Anxiety Scale (CMAS-R; Portuguese version by Dias & Gonçalves, 1999) was applied. This scale evaluated the global anxiety index and the global lie index. Anxiety was assessed using 28 items ranging from a minimum of 0 to a maximum of 28 points. The global lie index was evaluated using 9 items, varying between a minimum of 0 and a maximum of 9 points. High values represent a high level of lying on the part of the participant. According to the authors, this instrument has good reliability as represented by a Cronbach's alpha of 0.80 (Dias & Gonçalves, 1999). The d2 Test of Attention was used to measure children's selective attention and concentration, through 14 lines, each with 47 stimuli (of the letters p and d accompanied by either one or two quotation marks or comma) from

which the participant must identify the letter "d" with two upper quotation marks (Brickenkamp & Zillmer, 2010). Through this instrument, it was possible to calculate the Total Processed Characters, PC (that is the number of stimuli indicated, taking into account the participant's speed, productivity, or motivation); the Total Hits, TH (that is the effectiveness in performing the task); the Total Effectiveness, TE (which measured the level of attentional control and the relationship between speed and accuracy throughout the task); the Concentration Index, CI (indicating the level of concentration in the task); the Variability Index, VI (which revealed whether the task was performed consistently or in a variable way); and Percentage of Errors, E% (which showed the accuracy and quality of performance). The Portuguese version of the instrument revealed a Cronbach's Alpha greater than 0.90 (Brickenkamp & Zillmer, 2010). Finally, the Arithmetic subtest of the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children (Portuguese version by Simões, 2002) was applied to assess the participants' calculus, logical-mathematical reasoning, and problem-solving skills through 24 items. The score varies between a minimum of 0 and a maximum of 24 points, with high scores reflecting good arithmetic and reasoning skills (Wechsler, 1991/2003; Simões, 2002). The Portuguese version of this subtest showed good internal consistency with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.84 (Simões, 2002).

Procedure

First, the directors of several sports clubs in the Lisbon region were contacted. The study objectives were presented to the directors and permission was sought to contact the athletes' legal representatives. After getting approval, the athletes' legal representatives were contacted. They were informed about the study's objectives, the confidentiality of the information collected, the voluntary nature of the investigation, and the ethical and deontological duties of the investigators. They were then asked to sign their informed consent. After authorization by the legal representatives, the athletes who were willing to participate were contacted. After this period, sessions were scheduled with the participants who were individually assessed. The protocol application site was a room belonging to the sports clubs that collaborated in the investigation. The researchers respected all ethical and deontological duties and there was no risk of any kind to the participants.

Data Analysis

For the present investigation, the statistical software R, R-Studio, was used for data analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to characterize the sample, specifically the analysis of means and standard deviations for quantitative variables and the analysis of frequencies and percentages for nominal variables. A Gamma Regression Model was used to study the response variable, using a logarithmic link function. The step function of R was also used to automatically select the covariates that should be included in the gamma model. The significance level assumed in this study was p -value < 0.05 .

Results

Prediction of Arithmetic Skills

The following table (Table 1) shows the coefficients of the explanatory variables of the athletes' arithmetic skills.

At the usual significance levels (5%), this model reveals that there is a significant covariate, namely anxiety symptoms. Residual deviations range from -0.43 to 0.40 and the calculated value of the residual deviation is

2.766 for 100 degrees of freedom. The measure of the quality of this adjustment given by the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) is 501.05.

Then, the covariates that should be included in the gamma model were automatically selected and a new adjustment value of the resulting model was performed. According to the new adjusted model (Table 2), the new coefficients and covariates of the model are identified.

Table 1

Variable Coefficients: Age, Anxiety Symptoms, Lie, Attention: Processed Characters, Attention: Hits, Attention: Default Errors, Attention: Errors by Marking Irrelevant Characters

Coefficients	Estimated value	SE	t-value	p-value
Intercept	2.139	0.122	17.423	<2e-16***
Age	0.007	0.009	0.77	0.44
Anxiety symptoms	-0.007	0.004	-2.06	0.04*
Lie	0.002	0.007	0.36	0.72
Attention, PC	0.001	0.002	0.45	0.66
Attention, Hits	0.002	0.006	0.25	0.80
Attention, DE	-0.003	0.006	-0.56	0.58
Attention, EMIC	-0.009	0.005	-1.91	0.06

Note. SE – standard error; p-value: *0.05; **0.01; ***0.001; PC – processed characters; DE – default errors; EMIC – errors by marking irrelevant characters.

Table 2

Variable Coefficients: Anxiety Symptoms, Attention: Processed Characters, Attention: Default Errors, Attention: Errors by Marking Irrelevant Characters

Coefficients	Estimated value	SE	t-value	p-value
Intercept	2.222	0.082	27.161	<2e-16***
Anxiety symptoms	-0.009	0.004	-2.48	0.015*
Attention, PC	0.002	0.000	8.86	2.51e-14***
Attention, DE	-0.005	0.001	-4.00	0.000***
Attention, EMIC	-0.009	0.005	-1.92	0.057

Note. SE – standard error; p-value: *0.05; **0.01; ***0.001; PC – processed characters; DE – default errors; EMIC – errors by marking irrelevant characters.

During the adjustment, three covariates were eliminated from the model, namely, age, lying, and the total number of hits of the attention task.

On the other hand, there were more significant covariates, a total of three new significant covariates, for the usual significance levels (5%). These variables are anxiety symptoms, the characters processed in the attention task, and the omission errors in the attention task. Residual deviations range from -0.43 to 0.39, with a residual deviation value of 2.740 with 103 degrees of freedom. The AIC value is 496.0. The p-value calculation to verify the suitability of this model shows a p-value=1. Considering the value of 1 obtained, it is accepted that this model is adequate and proves to be better than the previous model.

Through the analysis of the residuals of the adjusted model (Figure 1), it is verified that the residuals are distributed around 0, with an amplitude that seems constant for the different adjusted values, without verifying any trend. This also indicates that this model fits this dataset well.

Figure 1

Representation of the Adjusted Model Residuals

Through the calculation of Cook's distances (Figure 2), the observations effectively influencing the model were verified. Thus, 3 effectively influential observations were identified, namely observations 15, 81, and 104, that is, a slight modification or exclusion of these observations from the model could cause significant changes in the estimates of the model parameters.

Figure 2
 Calculation Results for Cook's Distances

Then, these three observations were removed from the model and the gamma model was adjusted again (Table 3).

Table 3

Variable Coefficients: Age, Anxiety Symptoms, Lie, Attention: Processed Characters, Attention: Hits, Attention: Default Errors, Attention: Errors by Marking Irrelevant Characters for Adjusted Sample

Coefficients	Estimated value	SE	t-value	p-value
Intercept	2.179	0.122	17.747	<2e-16***
Age	0.006	0.009	0.72	0.48
Anxiety symptoms	-0.008	0.004	-2.26	0.03*
Lie	0.002	0.007	0.31	0.76
Attention, PC	0.001	0.002	0.47	0.64
Attention, Hits	0.001	0.007	0.16	0.87
Attention, DE	-0.003	0.006	-0.56	0.58
Attention, EMIC	-0.016	0.005	-3.06	0.003**

Note. SE – standard error; p-value: *0.05; **0.01; ***0.001; PC – processed characters; DE – default errors; EMIC – errors by marking irrelevant characters.

Table 4

Variable Coefficients: Anxiety Symptoms, Attention: Processed Characters, Attention: Default Errors, Attention: Errors by Marking Irrelevant Characters for Adjusted Sample

Coefficients	Estimated value	SE	t-value	p-value
Intercept	2.25	0.081	27.824	<2e-16***
Anxiety symptoms	-0.009	0.003	-2.664	0.009**
Attention, PC	0.002	0.000	8.84	3.44e-14***
Attention, DE	-0.005	0.001	-3.52	0.000***
Attention, EMIC	-0.016	0.005	-3.088	0.003**

Note. SE – standard error; p-value: *0.05; **0.01; ***0.001; PC – processed characters; DE – default errors; EMIC – errors by marking irrelevant characters.

In this new adjustment, three covariates were eliminated, namely, age, lying, and the total number of hits of the attention task. With this new adjustment, there were now four significant covariates: anxiety symptoms, characters processed in the attention task, errors by omission, and errors by marking irrelevant characters in the attention task. Residual deviations range from -0.43140 to 0.37738. The AIC value is 475.34 and the residual deviation value is 2.5450 with 100 degrees of freedom. The value of p -value=1 and, for this reason, it is accepted that this model is adequate. The analysis of the model's residuals (Figure 3) shows that the residuals are distributed around 0, which indicates that this model fits well with this data set.

Comparing this model with the previously adjusted model, this model turns out to be better than the previous one for this dataset.

The sample now has 105 participants.

In this model, it appears that there are two significant covariates, namely, anxiety symptoms and errors by marking irrelevant characters.

Residual deviations range from -0.42871 to 0.39180. The AIC value is 480.56 and the residual deviation value is 2.5263 for 97 degrees of freedom. The suitability analysis of this model shows a p -value=1.

According to the value of 1 obtained, the hypothesis that this regression model is adequate is not rejected.

Then, a new value of the adjustment of the model was carried out, from which the covariates to be included in the gamma model were automatically selected.

The set of covariates and their coefficients obtained with the newly adjusted model are shown in Table 4.

Figure 3

Representation of the Residuals of the New Adjusted Model

Discussion

The primary aim of this investigation was to ascertain whether indicators of anxiety symptoms, deceptive behavior, attentional capacity, and age could serve as predictive factors for arithmetic proficiency among children engaged in sporting activities.

Our findings demonstrated that manifestations of anxiety symptoms, processing of characters during the attentional task, instances of omission errors, and errors associated with marking irrelevant characters in the attention assessment all function as predictors for arithmetic aptitude in the child and adolescent demographic.

Drawing from the research conducted by Wu et al. (2017), it was established that in eight-year-old children, the presence of math-related anxiety exerted a noteworthy and consistent indirect impact on nonverbal performance in numerical operations and mathematical reasoning. Furthermore, in tasks of heightened complexity, mathematical anxiety exhibited both direct and indirect effects (via working memory) on mathematical reasoning abilities. Conversely, it was posited that the adoption of cognitive reappraisal strategies for mathematical tasks, resulting in diminished negative affect and amygdala responses to anxiety-inducing situations, could lead to a reduction in anxiety levels, thereby potentially enhancing mathematical performance (Pizzie et al., 2020). In accordance with Wu et al. (2017) findings, instances where children experience anxiety pertaining to arithmetic tasks may paradoxically lead to heightened attentional investment in the tasks, thereby substantiating the notion that anxiety's presence may not invariably yield detrimental outcomes. However, it should be noted that the presence of math-related anxiety may impede the exclusion of distracting environmental stimuli from one's focus, irrespective of the mathematical content involved (Hopko et al., 2002). This phenomenon, as elucidated by our observations, could contribute to an increased frequency of errors on the part of participants in the tasks, specifically encompassing default errors and errors arising from the misidentification of irrelevant characters during the attentional assessment. Instances of compromised focused attention, difficulties in the effective utilization of well-practiced information (e.g., basic addition or multiplication facts), or challenges in the ability to deploy and switch between diverse mathematical processes for problem-solving, collectively illuminate the adverse influence of attentional limitations on arithmetic competencies (Wu et al., 2017). Regarding the characters processed within the attention task, it has been established that these also hold predictive value for the participants' arithmetic proficiencies. A study conducted by Anobile et al. (2013) involving a cohort of 68 children aged between 8 and 11 years revealed that attentional and perceptual competencies pertaining to numerical concepts emerged as predictive indicators for the participants' mathematical scores. Even subsequent to controlling for the influence of other pertinent variables, these researchers noted that attentional faculties exhibited a sustained association with

mathematical aptitude and the discernment of numerical quantities. Wong and Liu (2020) similarly affirmed that goal-directed visual attention correlated with children's arithmetic capabilities, with this connection being mediated by the subjects' enumeration proficiencies. Furthermore, our findings indicate that deceitful behavior and age do not bear significant relevance as predictors of arithmetic abilities. Costa & Pinho (2010) did not establish a notable correlation between dishonesty and arithmetic performance. However, Maggioni & Rossignoli (2020) did discern such a relationship. As children undergo cognitive maturation, they acquire the capacity to adopt inaccurate behaviors and engage in deception for competitive advantage, as delineated by Ding et al. (2018). In regard to age, despite Aragón et al. (2018) contention that arithmetic skills tend to advance in tandem with educational progression and age, such a sociodemographic parameter did not manifest as a pertinent predictor variable for arithmetic performance in our analyzed sample. While a certain nexus between subjects' age and their arithmetic aptitude might be apparent (Nogues & Duro, 2016), other factors like the intensity of physical demands inherent to training regimens could exert a more salient influence upon cognitive proficiencies, particularly within the realm of arithmetic, as asserted by Coe et al. (2006). The implications of this study extend to sports clubs and similar organizations, offering insights for designing interventions aimed at bolstering cognitive capacities, particularly attentional and arithmetic proficiencies, while concurrently fostering emotional regulation among athletes, given their pronounced impact on athletic performance. However, it should be acknowledged that this study did not account for the potential effects stemming from other cognitive variables, such as working memory, which could impinge upon attentional capabilities (Orbach et al., 2020), consequently influencing the resolution of arithmetic tasks (Michel et al., 2020). Additionally, the potential influence of negative affect on task performance among participants remained unexamined (Storbeck & Clore, 2007). Subsequent research endeavors should endeavor to delineate more precise participant characteristics concerning this task domain, thereby enhancing control over potentially influential variables within analytical models, as well as probing the ramifications of psychological symptoms on the mathematical proficiencies of youth engaged in sports.

Conclusions

This study allows for the conclusion that the presence of anxiety and attentional characteristics such as processing of characters during the attentional task, instances of omission errors and errors by marking irrelevant characters hold predictive power over the arithmetic abilities of the youth.

This type of variables is important for the sports performance of young individuals and should be integrated into training and development programs for athletes to help them maximize their athletic performance.

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Ethical Approval

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**SOCIAL AND
BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES**

Psychology

SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES. Psychology

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

The Impact of the War in Ukraine on the Psychological Well-Being of Students

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
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Abstract

The war in Ukraine affects the psychological state and life activities of university students. Aim of the study: to identify the state of psychological well-being of students and the peculiarities of students' use of coping strategies in overcoming life crises on their own.

The study was conducted among 323 Ukrainian university students aged 20-35 in October 2023. According to the impact of the hostilities on them, the respondents were divided into 3 groups: Group 1 – 111 persons living in the area of active hostilities; Group 2 – 104 persons living in the areas where missiles and drones were fired; Group 3 – 108 persons living on the territory of Ukraine, where there were no hostilities and shelling, and in the EU countries. The Psychological General Well-Being Index, PGWBI, and the Coping Strategies Inventory, CSI, were included in an online survey. Both techniques were found to have adequate internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha was 0.928 and 0.759, respectively).

Respondents in all groups are moderately distressed. The highest level of distress (the lowest level of PGWBI) was found among students in Group 1 (55.1 points). Students in Groups 2 and 3 had lower scores (60.1 and 63.5 points, respectively), which corresponds to moderate distress. Students use a variety of coping strategies in stressful situations. However, the coping strategy of cognitive restructuring was used more often (9.8 points in Group 3, 9.5 points in Group 1). This was due to a general rethinking of the meaning of life, of attitudes toward oneself and others because of the war. Coping strategies of social support (8.9 points) and self-criticism (8.7 points) were also important for Group 1. This was due to the importance of social support, reassessment of one's own behavior and thinking in the war.

The obtained data indicate that the war in Ukraine has a negative impact on the psychological state of students. The level of impact was higher the closer the students were to the active combat zone. This influence determined the students' choice of coping strategies in dealing with life crises on their own.

students, psychological well-being, distress, coping strategy, war

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Introduction

The war in Ukraine affects both the physical health and psychological well-being of individuals and communities. Despite the relatively long period of martial law (20 months), most Ukrainians are still in the epicenter of active hostilities. People are killed and injured as a result of the constant bombardment of public places by Russian missiles and drones, the usual way of life is disrupted, and there is often no communication, water, heat or electricity (Stadnik et al., 2022).

Although a part of the population of Ukraine lives in safer regions or abroad, millions of Ukrainians have become internally displaced persons, migrants (Patel & Erickson, 2022).

Recent studies show that many Ukrainians have lost their homes, jobs, money, property, parents and relatives, and have mental health problems (Ben-Ezra et al., 2023; Stadnik et al., 2023).

Data from the WHO World Mental Health Surveys have highlighted that recovery from post-traumatic stress disorder is particularly slow in the context of war (Koenen et al., 2017).

War causes trauma to both its participants and the wider community (Surzykiewicz et al., 2022). One of the most vulnerable categories is the student youth, who are forced to endure all the hardships and difficulties of war. In addition, university study is a period of adult formation characterized by dramatic psychosocial changes, problems related to learning, interpersonal relationships, and the need to adapt to student life.

As a result, the combination of these factors can have a significant impact on learning outcomes, as well as on students' health and psychological well-being.

To achieve a sufficient level of psychological well-being, it is necessary to learn how to use constructive and effective coping strategies (Pérez-Chacón et al., 2023). Appropriate coping strategies help students to deal with life's difficulties and obstacles and to find adaptive opportunities in stressful situations. However, poorly chosen coping strategies can not only cause situational failure, but also perpetuate destructive ways of dealing with difficult life situations. As a result, it can lead to mental health problems (Yeh et al., 2023). In times of war, this is especially important for students.

Therefore, ignorance of protective behavior patterns (or the psychological mechanisms for dealing with difficult situations) can be a trigger for the onset of psychosomatic illness and other psychogenic personality disorders.

The aim of the study. To determine the impact of the war in Ukraine on the psychological well-being of university students and to identify the peculiarities of their use of coping strategies in overcoming life crises on their own. This study will allow us to better understand the key factors that affect the psychological state of students, develop appropriate measures of psychological support and psychoprophylaxis for students, and help optimize education at universities under martial law.

Materials and Methods

To conduct the study, we engaged Ukrainian students of Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs (KhNUIA) and Uzhhorod National University (UzhNU) in October 2023.

The participants are between the ages of 20 and 35 years old. All participants were divided into the following 3 groups:

Group 1 – students living in the area of active hostilities (Kharkiv region of Ukraine) in the amount of 111 persons, including 33 (29.7%) males and 78 (70.3%) females.

Group 2 – students living in the areas of Ukraine where there were shelling by missiles and drones and who are internally displaced persons, in the amount of 104 persons, including 19 (18.3%) males and 85 (81.7%) females.

Group 3 – students living in the areas where there were no hostilities and shelling (Transcarpathian region of Ukraine and the EU countries), in the amount of 108 persons, including 16 (14.8%) males and 92 (85.2%) females.

Due to the war in Ukraine, the study was conducted online. The psychological tests were posted on the official website of the Scientific Research Institute KRPOCH (2023), using Google Forms for potential participants. In addition, all groups were monitored during remote and face-to-face classes. An individual interview was used when it was necessary.

The following techniques were used to achieve the research goal: Psychological General Well-Being Index – PGWBI (Grossi & Compare, 2014) and Coping Strategies Inventory – CSI (Tobin et al., 1989).

Psychological well-being was assessed using the Ukrainian version of the 22-item Psychological General Well-Being Index questionnaire (<https://forms.gle/MG5nmrydPo5Ff3Tx5>). This self-assessment tool is designed to measure subjective well-being or suffering over the past 4 weeks. It explores six different domains: Anxiety (ANX), Depressive Mood (DEP), Positive Well-Being (PWB), Self-Control (SC), General Health (GH), and Vitality (VT). Each item was rated on a 6-point scale (from 0 to 5). The global summary score was calculated by dividing the raw score obtained during the test by the maximum raw score obtained for each parameter and multiplying the result by 100. Higher scores indicate a better PGWBI. More specifically, a total score of less than 55 points indicates severe distress, 55-65 points indicates moderate distress, and 66-100 points indicates no distress or a state of psychological well-being. High scores on ANX and DEP indicate low anxiety and low depression, while high scores on PWB, SC, GH, and VT indicate high positive well-being, self-control, good general health, and vitality.

Coping strategies were assessed using the Ukrainian version of the 32-item Coping Strategies Inventory (<https://forms.gle/PHxRXbtVRhx35M2s5>).

The primary subscale of coping strategies includes the following items: Problem Solving (PS), Cognitive Restructuring (CR), Express Emotions (EE), Social Support (SS), Problem Avoidance (PA), Wishful Thinking (WT), Self-Criticism (SC), and Social Withdrawal (SW). The secondary subscale of coping strategies includes the following items: Problem-Focused Engagement (PFE), Problem-Focused Disengagement (PFD), Emotion-Focused Engagement (EFE), and Emotion-Focused Disengagement (EFD). The tertiary subscale of coping strategies includes the first tier items: Engagement (E) and Disengagement (D), as well as the second tier items: problem-focused and emotion-focused engagement, problem-focused and emotion-focused disengagement.

To calculate the secondary and tertiary subscale scores, the scores of the relevant items on the primary subscale are summed. Each item was rated on a 5-point Likert scale. Respondents were asked to rate the overall frequency with which they use each coping strategy

listed on the survey, indicating their choices as follows: 1 = "Never", 2 = "Seldom", 3 = "Sometimes", 4 = "Often" and 5 = "Almost Always". Higher scores reflect greater use of the relevant coping strategy.

Statistical analysis were calculated using SPSS 27.0 software. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics procedures, using frequencies, means and standard deviations. Internal consistency was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. To assess the associations between the scales, the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated.

Results

Mean scores for all items and the global summary measures were calculated according to the first technique (PGWBI). The general results of psychological well-being by the scales of anxiety, depressive mood, positive well-being, self-control, general health, and vitality of Ukrainian universities students during the war are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

The Scores of Psychological Well-Being by Domains (Anxiety, Depressive Mood, Positive Well-Being, Self-Control, General Health, and Vitality) for Students of the Ukrainian Universities during the War (Points)

Group	Anxiety	Depressive Mood	Positive Well-Being	Self-Control	General Health	Vitality	Global
Group 1	52.7	60.6	52.4	54.4	62.7	52.4	55.1
Group 2	55.5	65.6	56.0	66.0	70.7	54.0	60.1
Group 3	58.6	71.8	58.4	68.7	74.1	56.6	63.5

Anxiety in students is related to the perception of tension and worry. The highest scores (less anxiety) on the ANX scale were found among students in Group 3 (58.6 points), which is lower than the scores of Group 2 (55.5 points). The lowest scores (more anxiety) were shown by students in Group 1 (52.7 points).

Depressive mood is a state of low mood and feelings of sadness and despair that can be caused by sleep disturbance and fatigue during war. Major depression may be a risk factor for suicide. The lowest scores on the DEP scale (with depression) were observed among students in Group 1 (60.6 points), and the highest scores (without depression) were observed among students in Group 3 (71.8 points). The data showed a significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between these groups.

Positive well-being refers to satisfaction with learning, work, and daily activities. The data obtained did not show a significant difference between the groups studied. Students in Group 1 perceived their learning and living conditions as more unsatisfactory than other groups, while students in Group 3 had the highest scores on the PWB scale (58.4 points).

Self-control means having the ability to control your emotions, behaviors, desires, confidence, and need to make difficult decisions. According to the SC scale, significant differences were found between students of Group 1 and Groups 2, 3 (54.4 and 66.0, 68.7 points, respectively). Students in Group 1 had the lowest scores (less self-control).

General health characterizes perceptions of health and

measures fear of illness and/or feeling too tired to study, which can interfere with learning. Students in Group 3 scored the highest on the GH scale (74.1 points), which is significantly higher than the scores of Group 1 (62.7 points) and Group 2 (70.7 points).

Vitality assesses mental and physical fatigue, apathy, loss of energy, and activity. According to the VT scale, the scores for the three groups of respondents did not differ significantly. The lowest scores (lower vitality) were for students in Group 1 (52.4 points), and the highest scores were for students in Group 3 (56.6 points).

The highest level of distress (the lowest level of PGWBI) was found among students in Group 1 (55.1 points). Students in Groups 2 and 3 had lower scores (60.1 and 63.5 points, respectively), which corresponds to moderate distress.

A comparison of gender differences (Figure 1) showed that male students scored higher than female students on almost all indicators of PGWBI technique, indicating a higher level of psychological well-being.

At the same time, female participants in Groups 2 and 3 scored higher on the DEP scale (66.8 and 72.2 points) than male participants (59.7 and 69.6 points). This indicates a low level of depression and stress. It should also be noted that women in Group 1 have rather low scores on the ANX (50.3 points), PWB (49.7 points), SC (53.4 points), and VT (47.9 points) scales. This indicates their great distress. The absence of distress on the GH scale was shown by men of all groups, indicating their

satisfactory general health. Men in Groups 2 and 3 have the highest global scores (67.5 and 67.3 points, respectively), indicating their state of no distress. The

lowest score of all gender groups (52.4 points), and thus the highest overall level of distress, is found among female students in Group 1.

Figure 1

The Scores of Psychological Well-Being by Gender of Students of the Ukrainian Universities during the War According to Six Scales (Points)

Note. ANX – Anxiety, DEP – Depressive Mood, PWB – Positive Well-Being, SC – Self-Control, GH – General Health, VT – Vitality.

The mean, standard error, standard deviation, and median of the total scores obtained from the PGWBI technique scales are summarized in Table 2. Cronbach’s alpha coefficients were computed for each of the six scales of the PGWBI to estimate internal consistency reliability (Table 2). All scales were found to have acceptable levels of reliability ($\alpha=0.689-0.843$).

Cronbach’s alpha for the total scale was 0.928. These scores indicate the homogeneity of the items in each of the dimensions of the scale.

Inter-item correlation matrix for PGWBI scales is shown in Table 3. The correlation indicated a strong, positive relationship between all items on the scale.

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics and Internal Consistency Reliability for PGWBI Scales (N=323)

Scales	Mean	Standard error of mean	Median	Standard deviation	Internal consistency reliability
Anxiety	55.49	1.124	64.00	20.19	0.843
Depressive Mood	65.86	1.203	73.33	21.61	0.741
Positive Well-Being	55.65	1.043	55.00	18.74	0.766
Self-Control	62.79	1.175	66.67	21.11	0.729
General Health	68.96	1.108	66.67	19.92	0.689
Vitality	54.12	0.996	55.00	17.90	0.814

Table 3

Inter-Item Correlation Matrix for PGWBI Scales

Scales	ANX	DEP	PWB	SC	GH	VT
ANX	1.000	0.703	0.825	0.787	0.649	0.811
DEP	0.703	1.000	0.550	0.615	0.691	0.623
PWB	0.825	0.550	1.000	0.761	0.548	0.788
SC	0.787	0.615	0.761	1.000	0.613	0.731
GH	0.649	0.691	0.548	0.613	1.000	0.630
VT	0.811	0.623	0.788	0.731	0.630	1.000

Note. ANX – Anxiety, DEP – Depressive Mood, PWB – Positive Well-Being, SC – Self-Control, GH – General Health, VT – Vitality.

The Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated to assess the associations between the scales (Table 4). Mean scores for all items and the global summary measures were calculated according to the second

technique (CSI). The level of use of coping strategies for the primary subscale by the students of the Ukrainian universities during the war, including gender differences, is shown in Figure 2.

Table 4
 Pearson Correlations for PGWBI Scales

Scales		ANX	DEP	PWB	SC	GH	VT
ANX	Pearson Correlation	1.000	0.703**	0.825**	0.787**	0.649**	0.811**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	-	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	N	323	323	323	323	323	323
DEP	Pearson Correlation	0.703**	1.000	0.550**	0.615**	0.691**	0.623**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	-	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	N	323	323	323	323	323	323
PWB	Pearson Correlation	0.825**	0.550**	1.000	0.761**	0.548**	0.788**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	<0.001	-	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	N	323	323	323	323	323	323
SC	Pearson Correlation	0.787**	0.615**	0.761**	1.000	0.613**	0.731**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	-	<0.001	<0.001
	N	323	323	323	323	323	323
GH	Pearson Correlation	0.649**	0.691**	0.548**	0.613**	1.000	0.630**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	-	<0.001
	N	323	323	323	323	323	323
VT	Pearson Correlation	0.811**	0.623**	0.788**	0.731**	0.630**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	-
	N	323	323	323	323	323	323

Note. ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); ANX – Anxiety, DEP – Depressive Mood, PWB – Positive Well-Being, SC – Self-Control, GH – General Health, VT – Vitality.

Figure 2
 Level of Use of Coping Strategies for the Primary Subscale by Ukrainian University Students during the War (Points)

Note. PS – Problem Solving, CR – Cognitive Restructuring, EE – Express Emotions, SS – Social Support, PA – Problem Avoidance, WT – Wishful Thinking, SC – Self-Criticism, SW – Social Withdrawal.

The highest coping strategy scores for all groups were for the CR coping strategy (10.0 points for Group 3, 9.6 points for Group 1, 9.4 points for Group 2). This demonstrates the importance of changing maladaptive thoughts to more appropriate ones in order to reduce the level of suffering. However, there are some differences in the scores of the groups studied, which may indicate certain peculiarities of the impact of proximity to the combat zone on students. Group 1 is characterized by the SC coping strategy

(9.2 points) in addition to the SS coping strategy (8.6 points). This is manifested in the independent search for mistakes, the evaluation of one's own behavior and the results of one's own thinking. In addition to social support (9.2 points for the SS coping strategy), Group 2 is characterized by wishful thinking (9.3 points for the WT coping strategy), which indicates that students' beliefs and decisions are formed according to what is pleasurable rather than according to rationality or reality.

For Group 3, expressing emotions (EE – 9.1 points) and social support (SS – 9.3 points) play an important role in overcoming anxiety and depression, which is manifested in expressive speech and behavior, physical and emotional help even to strangers.

Representatives of all groups have the lowest scores on the social withdrawal subscale: 6.2 points in Group 3, 6.4 points in Group 1, and 6.5 points in Group 2 for the SW coping strategy. This demonstrates the ineffectiveness of this coping strategy in dealing with the stress of war.

Gender differences include the predominance of the CR coping strategy for men in all groups studied. For women in Group 1, self-critical coping (SC – 9.5 points) is typical, Group 2 is characterized by wishful thinking (WT – 9.1 points), and Group 3 is characterized by emotional coping (EE – 9.2 points) and cognitive restructuring coping (CR – 9.7 points).

Students' use of coping strategies for the secondary subscale is characterized as follows (Figure 3).

Figure 3

Level of Use of Coping Strategies for the Secondary Subscale by Ukrainian University Students during the War (Points)

Note. PFE – Problem-Focused Engagement, PFD – Problem-Focused Disengagement, EFE – Emotion-Focused Engagement, EFD – Emotion-Focused Disengagement

The highest scores among students of all groups are for coping strategies of emotion-focused engagement EFE (18.4 points for Group 3 and 18.1 points for Group 2) and problem-focused engagement PFE (18.2 points for Group 3 and 17.5 points for Group 1), which shows the importance of managing emotions and problems to overcome the effects of stress. At the same time, Group 2 is more likely to use a PFE coping strategy (17.2 points), and Group 1 is more likely to use an EFE coping strategy (17.0 points), which indicates a more

active assimilation of these strategies by the respective categories of students. EFD coping strategies are the least used by all groups (15.6 points, 15.5 points, and 15.0 points for Groups 1, 2, and 3, respectively).

Gender differences include more frequent use of problem-focused engagement coping strategies by men in all groups. While for women, it is a coping strategy of emotion-focused engagement.

The level of use of coping strategies for the tertiary subscale by the students is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4

Level of Use of Coping Strategies for the Tertiary Subscale by Ukrainian University Students during the War (Points)

Students in all groups used engagement (E) coping strategies more often (34.5 points, 35.3 points, and 36.7 points for Groups 1, 2, and 3, respectively). At the same time, the gap in the use of disengagement (D) coping strategies is the smallest in Group 3, indicating

the ineffectiveness of coping with stress through engagement strategies among students in this group. The mean, standard error, standard deviation, and median of the total scores obtained on the subscales of the CSI technique are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5

Descriptive Statistics for the Secondary and the Tertiary Subscales of the CSI and Internal Consistency Reliability

Items of subscale	N	Mean	Standard error of mean	Median	Standard deviation	Range	Internal consistency reliability
PFE	323	17.73	0.305	18.00	5.48	23	0.795
PFD	323	16.46	0.284	16.00	5.11	22	0.739
EFE	323	17.86	0.320	18.00	5.75	20	0.844
EFD	323	15.31	0.269	14.00	4.83	18	0.672
E	323	35.59	0.545	36.00	9.80	39	0.820
D	323	31.77	0.477	30.00	8.57	34	0.706

Note. PFE – Problem-Focused Engagement, PFD – Problem-Focused Disengagement, EFE – Emotion-Focused Engagement, EFD – Emotion-Focused Disengagement, E – Engagement, D – Disengagement.

Cronbach’s Alpha coefficients were computed for each of the secondary and the tertiary subscales of the CSI to estimate internal consistency reliability (Table 5). Acceptable internal consistency was seen for all subscales. Cronbach’s alpha coefficients ranged from 0.672 to 0.844 for the secondary subscale, which are Problem-Focused Engagement, Problem-Focused Disengagement, Emotion-Focused Engagement, and

Emotion-Focused Disengagement, and 0.820 and 0.706 for the tertiary subscale, Engagement and Disengagement respectively. Cronbach’s alpha for the total scale was 0.759. These scores indicate the homogeneity of the items in each subscale. To assess the associations between the secondary and tertiary subscales, the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated (Table 6).

Table 6

Pearson Correlations for the Secondary and the Tertiary Subscales of the CSI

Items of subscale	PFE	EFE	PFD	EFD	E	D	
PFE	Pearson Correlation	1.000	0.522**	-0.372**	-0.327**	0.865**	-0.406**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	-	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	N	323	323	323	323	323	323
EFE	Pearson Correlation	0.522**	1.000	-0.076	-0.161**	0.879**	-0.136*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	-	0.173	0.004	<0.001	0.014
	N	323	323	323	323	323	323
PFD	Pearson Correlation	-0.372**	-0.076	1	0.486**	-0.252**	0.870**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	0.173	-	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001
	N	323	323	323	323	323	323
EFD	Pearson Correlation	-0.327**	-0.161**	0.486**	1.000	-0.277**	0.854**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	0.004	<0.001	-	<0.001	<0.001
	N	323	323	323	323	323	323
E	Pearson Correlation	0.865**	0.879**	-0.252**	-0.277**	1.000	-0.307**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	-	<0.001
	N	323	323	323	323	323	323
D	Pearson Correlation	-0.406**	-0.136*	0.870**	0.854**	-0.307**	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	<0.001	0.014	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	-
	N	323	323	323	323	323	323

Note. ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed); PFE – Problem-Focused Engagement, PFD – Problem-Focused Disengagement, EFE – Emotion-Focused Engagement, EFD – Emotion-Focused Disengagement, E – Engagement, D – Disengagement.

Discussion

This research is part of a comprehensive study of mental health in the extreme conditions of low-intensity war,

martial law, and full-scale war in Ukraine, which has been ongoing since 2014. Previous studies (Melnyk et al., 2019) have examined the

impact of extreme conditions of low-intensity warfare on military personnel. It was found that the level of resistance of military personnel to combat psychological trauma depends on the impact of extreme conditions (participation in combat operations). There is a high probability of mental disorders, a tendency to personality dysfunction, behavioral and activity disorders, even with slight exposure to extreme conditions (lack of combat experience). The COVID-19 pandemic has added extreme conditions to the already existing conditions of low-intensity warfare in our study of the mental health of military personnel and students. These new conditions made it possible to find out that military personnel with combat experience were significantly less likely to suffer from anxiety, depression, and stress and sleep disorders than military personnel without such experience (Melnyk et al., 2020; Melnyk & Stadnik, 2020). We assumed that the mental health of students in low-intensity war and extreme pandemic conditions would be significantly different from that of trained military personnel. For this reason, we studied only those students who participated in sports. It was found that most students had a moderate level of mental health, about a third had a high level of mental health, and less than 10% had a low level of mental health (Melnyk et al., 2022). Other researchers have found similar results regarding the positive effects of physical activity and sports on the mental health of probationers during this period (Klaus et al., 2023; Senışık et al., 2021). These studies confirm the fact that systematic physical activity has a positive effect on mental health, even under the extreme conditions of a pandemic and/or low-intensity war. The positive role of physical activity on students' mental health has been demonstrated in numerous studies (Biddle et al., 2019; Mahindru et al., 2023; Tyson et al., 2010; White et al., 2017), including in the extreme conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic (Lee et al., 2021; Lukács, 2021; Savage et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2020).

Studies of student youth in the context of a full-blown war show that the greatest psychogenias are the following: risk of death of relatives, family, separation from relatives, family, lack of work or other source of income, fear of death and risk of loss of property. Associations have also been found between psychological distress and chronic fatigue and sleep disturbances (Stadnik et al., 2022). The relationship between the above aspects is bidirectional, as symptoms can be both a source and a consequence of psychological distress. In addition, the dependence of the psychological state of the students on their physical proximity to the combat zone was revealed. The closer students were to the combat zone, the greater the negative impact on their mental health (Stadnik et al., 2023).

As an extension of previous research on student mental health, this paper focuses on the following understudied aspect of the problem – analysis of the psychological well-being of university students and their choice of coping strategies in overcoming life crises in the context of the war in Ukraine. We took into account our earlier data on the effectiveness of the study by dividing the entire sample of students into groups based on their

proximity to the combat zone.

An important feature of the present study is the following:

- Group 1 was located in an active war zone. During the first 600 days of the full-scale war, the duration of alarms for Kharkiv region amounted to 99 days and nights, 18 hours and 11 minutes, and part of the territory was occupied.

- Group 2 was under the influence of war stressors at the time of the survey. However, this proved to be less significant and the territories were not occupied.

- Group 3 included Ukrainian students residing in Ukraine with the status of internally displaced persons and in EU countries with the status of temporary protection.

Marchi et al. (2022) studied the problems of refugees and migrants in Europe and found that the study participants experienced psychological stress leading to mental health problems. War-related population movements have a negative impact on mental health, which is regularly confirmed by numerous studies (Ben-Ezra et al., 2023; Bogic et al., 2015; Bryant et al., 2022; Mesa-Vieira et al., 2022).

The unprecedented scale of Russian aggression against Ukraine has caused the largest mass displacement of people in modern history (Patel & Erickson, 2022). Studies show that asylum seekers and refugees are particularly vulnerable to traumatic experiences, which are of a threefold nature: pre-migration, peri-migration and post-migration. (Chen et al., 2017). According to the researchers (Michalek et al., 2022), the experience of war and displacement can have profound effects on children's affective development and mental health. However, the mechanisms underlying these effects remain unknown.

The relevance of certain psychological symptoms (anxiety, depression, insomnia, feeling of poor health) among civilians during war is widely recognized by Carpinello (2023); Morina et al. (2018).

Contemporary studies during the Russian-Ukrainian war have shown high prevalence rates of symptoms of psychological distress, anxiety, depression, and insomnia among Ukrainians aged 18 years and older. In addition, the scientists emphasize the need for further research and the development of effective survival strategies for Ukrainians during the war (Khraban, 2022; Xu et al., 2023).

The real need and problem that was identified in the scientific literature, but not solved in practice, determined the choice of the research subject and the techniques we used. In research and practice, the PGWBI and CSI are effective and valid tools.

The PGWBI is widely used in modern research (Gonzales et al., 2023; Maugeria et al., 2020). It also allows analysis and comparison of the data obtained.

Our research has shown that students in Group 1, where the constant shelling causes tension, anxiety, and dissatisfaction with daily activities, have the lowest scores on the anxiety and well-being scales. At the same time, the highest rates of general health are observed among students of Group 3. This shows that poor mood and fatigue have minimal impact on learning outcomes.

The Psychological General Well-Being Index was quite low for most of the students surveyed, due to the presence of many psychogenias caused by the war. This includes shelling of public places, hospitals, schools, energy and supply facilities, resulting in prolonged lack of water, heat, electricity and communications. Representatives of all student groups are moderately distressed. The highest level of distress (the lowest level of PGWBI) was found among students in Group 1 (55.1 points), in the area where active hostilities are taking place. Students in Groups 2 and 3 had lower levels of distress (60.1 points and 63.5 points, respectively), but distress was still in the range of moderate distress for this technique. Only men in all groups showed no distress on a separate scale (general health), indicating their satisfactory general health and well-being. The highest distress (lowest score of all groups) on the positive well-being scale was reported by female students in Group 1 (49.7 points). We believe that this is due to certain psychological characteristics and social roles of women, as well as the fact that they often witness numerous civilian casualties during war.

Previous work using the PGWBI has also largely indicated gender differences, with female students reporting higher levels of distress than male students (De la Rosa et al., 2022).

The use of other research techniques (the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales, DASS-21; General Health Questionnaire, GHQ-28; and the Social Support Questionnaire, F-SozU K-22) in the context of dividing students into groups according to their proximity to the combat zone allowed us to obtain similar results: the manifestations of depression were higher among women than among men. At the same time, severe and extremely severe manifestations of anxiety (2-3 times higher than similar indicators of respondents) were observed among students who were not in the vicinity of the combat zone (Stadnik et al., 2022, 2023). Thus, using different techniques to study this problem leads to similar results. The war had a significant negative impact on the mental state of the students, and the closer they were to the war zone, the greater the impact.

In the study, we took into account the particularities of student youth. For students, studying at a university is usually characterized by drastic psychosocial changes related to interpersonal relationships and the need to adapt to student life. Therefore, not only the effects of war, but also various social aspects of a student's life can significantly affect his or her ability to learn and lead to a deterioration of psychological well-being.

Previous research on the impact of the Russian-Ukrainian war on the mental health of student youth in Ukraine described by predictors determining the impact of specific features of the style of interpersonal behavior on the index of perceived stress, index of coping resources, positive attitude toward others, autonomy, environmental management, personal development, life goals, self-perception, psychological well-being, integration, control, risk acceptance and resilience (Lunov et al., 2023). Effects are also identified and characterized by levels of mental health impact: acute reactions – acute

disorder – chronic stress/disorder both on both personal and societal levels (Vus & Esterlis, 2022). Gilreath et al. (2022) studied stressors that can affect the academic performance and well-being of youth in wartime conditions.

Therefore, it is particularly important to study the strategies that students use to cope with stressful situations under difficult wartime conditions. Coping strategies are different ways of dealing with a stressful situation and are important for everyone's mental health. Furthermore, adaptive coping styles lead to improved mental health, while maladaptive coping styles lead to further deprivation and other mental health problems.

We chose the CSI questionnaire to study coping strategies because it is a reliable, proven, and widely used technique in research for assessing thoughts and behaviors that arise in response to a particular stressor (Pérez-Chacón et al., 2023; Yeh et al., 2023). As a particular type of social behavior, stress coping can either ensure or destroy a person's health and well-being. It allows the subject to cope with stress or inability to function in difficult life situations by being aware of their own actions. In addition, such behavior is aimed at actively interacting with the situation, i.e., changing it (if it is under control) or adapting to it (if it is not under control).

Our research has shown that university students use different coping strategies in the stressful situations of the war in Ukraine. However, the coping strategy of cognitive restructuring is more commonly used. It should also be noted that Group 1 is characterized by coping strategies of social support and self-criticism.

This study has some limitations. First of all, it should be noted that the study was conducted under conditions of active war, which may be the reason for the high values. Another limitation of our study is the small number of participants in each group. A more complex assessment of the students was not possible under these conditions. In our study of Ukrainian students, we used only the Ukrainian language versions of the PGWBI and CSI questionnaires. These versions of the questionnaires eliminated potential errors in question interpretation and optimized response time. Nevertheless, this provided important information that gives a first glimpse into the mental health status of the sample. It also made it possible to draw conclusions that help to take early measures aimed at improving the state of psychological well-being of students, taking into account the peculiarities of the use of coping strategies that they use to overcome life crises.

Conclusions

Thus, the war in Ukraine negatively affects the psychological well-being of university students – the closer they are to the combat zone, the greater the impact. This influence is also reflected in their use of coping strategies to manage life crises on their own.

The findings add to the knowledge of resources that need to be developed to increase students' resilience and psychological well-being. It can also become the basis for developing modern methods of social and

psychological support for students affected by the war. These methods should be comprehensive and involve the active collaboration of educational stakeholders in developing strategies to overcome difficulties, taking into account the individual psychological, social and cultural characteristics of students. This complex approach can play an important role in developing a sense of security, individual empowerment and “getting back on track”.

The results of the study point to the need for further research on student youth living in areas of active hostilities to determine the long-term consequences of this exposure on their psychological state, as well as the possibilities for optimizing education at universities under martial law.

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Ethical Approval

The study protocol was consistent with the ethical guidelines of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki as reflected in a prior approval by the Institution’s Human Research Committee. Permission for research received in the Research Committee of virtue and ethics Scientific Research Institute KRPOCH (protocol No. 023-1/SRI-KRPOCH dated 10.08.2023). Informed consent was sought from all the participants.

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SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES. Psychology

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

The Personality Traits of Family Caregivers of Individuals with Dementia: The Effects of Social Anxiety, Social Phobia, and Caregiving Hours

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
- G – Funds collection

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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

Caring for individuals afflicted with dementia engenders substantial demands and responsibilities for caregivers, encompassing the extensive time allocation devoted to the care recipient on a daily basis. Furthermore, the psychological attributes inherent in informal caregivers, encompassing traits like social anxiety and social phobia, can exert an influence on the evolution of their personal dynamics over time. This phenomenon potentially yields repercussions for how caregivers offer guidance and assistance to elderly individuals grappling with dementia, particularly in relation to their fundamental daily activities and instrumental tasks. The aim of the study: to analyze the predictive effect of social anxiety and social phobia as psychological characteristics of caregivers, along with the impact of caregiving hours as caregiving-related characteristics, on caregivers' personality.

Material and Methods:

This observational and cross-sectional study comprised a sample of 97 participants serving as primary family caregivers completed a sociodemographic questionnaire, the Big Five Inventory, the Anxiety Scale in Social Interaction Situations, and the Social Phobia Scale.

Results:

The findings revealed that social phobia demonstrated significant predictive power for Openness ($\beta=-0.199$; $p=0.016$) and Extraversion ($\beta=-0.136$; $p=0.024$), whereas the daily caregiving hours negatively affected Conscientiousness ($\beta=-0.145$; $p=0.011$), Agreeableness ($\beta=-0.137$; $p=0.040$), Openness ($\beta=-0.210$; $p=0.011$), and Extraversion ($\beta=-0.175$; $p=0.003$). Conversely, social anxiety did not prove to be a significant variable.

Conclusions:

The presence of social phobia or higher hours devoted to caregiving for individuals with dementia are factors that impact personality functioning and should be considered in the planning of support programs for family caregivers.

Keywords:

personality, informal caregivers, dementia, social phobia, social anxiety

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Introduction

Dementia is a brain disorder that affects the functioning of the nervous system and, consequently, impairs cognitive functions such as memory, language, reasoning, among others. According to the World Health Organization (2015), in 2015, an estimated 47.5 million people were affected by this neurological condition, and this number is expected to increase over time due to population aging. The progressive nature of this disease leads to the patient also losing social, functional, and behavioral abilities, necessitating supervision and support from caregivers. Informal caregivers are predominantly family members, often women, such as wives or daughters, who provide assistance with various daily tasks to the patient (e.g., hygiene, dressing, or feeding), dedicating several hours per day, without receiving monetary compensation for their efforts. Caregivers offer essential support not only in terms of basic and instrumental activities of daily living but also assume the responsibility of enhancing psychological well-being and quality of life for the patients (Serra et al., 2018; Silva et al., 2013). The demand for informal caregivers seems to be escalating, with a projected estimate of 21.5 million caregivers by the year 2030, with caregivers expected to dedicate at least 20 hours per week to caregiving responsibilities (Silva et al., 2013). Providing care for an individual with dementia necessitates empathy, flexibility, and patience; however, the approach taken by caregivers in executing their caregiving duties may also correlate with their personality traits (Melo et al., 2011). The psychological characteristics that underlie one's way of thinking, feeling, and acting, as well as the patterns found in attitudes and behaviors, define their personality (Flores-Mendoza & Colom, 2006). According to the Five Factor Model, the personality traits are extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness to experience. Each trait represents a continuum where each individual positions themselves, helping to define their personality (Schultz & Schultz, 2021; Tew et al., 2013) demonstrated that the presence of conscientiousness is associated with better physical, psychological, and social quality of life, while the presence of extraversion promotes better mental health among individuals. On the other hand, higher levels of neuroticism negatively affect physical health, mental well-being, social relationships, and environmental aspects. The caregiver's neuroticism for a person with dementia has a negative impact on their family functioning, while extraversion, agreeableness, and conscientiousness have a positive impact on the same family functioning (Tavares et al., 2020). Throughout the caregiving process, caregivers with traits such as optimism, extraversion, conscientiousness, and openness tend to employ more engagement coping strategies in dealing with daily situations, whereas the presence of neuroticism is associated with disengagement coping (Carver & Connor-Smith, 2010). Melo et al. (2016) found that the presence of various personality traits in caregivers leads them to use different strategies in handling the behavioral changes

of individuals with dementia. In their study, where caregivers spent approximately 12.2 hours per day on caregiving, when they used adaptive strategies with the patient (e.g., guiding the patient), the care provided to the individual with dementia was positive. Conversely, when caregivers used maladaptive strategies that were poorly suited to caregiving (e.g., confronting the patient), the quality of care was negatively affected. The presence of neuroticism may lead individuals to experience greater difficulty in coping with stressful, uncomfortable, or anxiety-inducing situations (Ji et al., 2022; Karaaslan et al., 2020), consequently negatively impacting the lives of those dependent on caregiving. This highlights the association between anxiety and individuals' personality traits. The presence of anxiety leads individuals to exhibit restlessness due to apprehensive anticipation of future situations (Ji et al., 2022). In the case of social anxiety, individuals perceive exposure to social interactions as problematic. Consequently, they tend to avoid such situations, which they perceive as threatening and where they might become the focus of others' attention (Morais et al., 2008). When the fear of these situations is experienced intensely, it can also manifest as social phobia. The presence of social phobia causes irrational fears and negative thoughts to impact individuals' functionality (Barlow, 2003), and a marked lack of sociability becomes prevalent in avoidant personality disorder (Pellecchia et al., 2018). Indeed, the existence of comorbidity between social phobia and avoidant personality disorder has been observed (Wittchen & Fehm, 2001), as well as a relationship between social phobia, shyness, and avoidant personality disorder (Botella et al., 2003), or a positive correlation between social anxiety and neuroticism, and a negative correlation with extroversion (Kaplan et al., 2015). However, the predictive effects of social phobia and social anxiety on different personality traits of caregivers remain unknown. Additionally, personality has also been associated with variables such as the patient's health status (Suso-Ribera et al., 2019), depression (Tavares et al., 2020), and caregiver burden (Kim et al., 2016; Tavares et al., 2020). Burden may manifest in later stages of caregiving, for instance, in female caregivers who dedicate 20 hours per week to caring for individuals with dementia, indicating that the time devoted to caregiving also has negative effects on caregivers' lives (Swinkels et al., 2019). However, it is not yet known how the time spent on caregiving may impact caregivers' personality functioning, despite acknowledging that personality can also undergo changes over time (Boyce et al., 2015). In light of this, our study hypothesis posits that social phobia and social anxiety may be important predictors of personality traits in family caregivers of individuals with dementia, and that the hours of care provided may also exert a similar effect.

The aim of the study. To investigate how social phobia, social anxiety, and daily caregiving hours significantly influence the personality characteristics of informal family caregivers of patients with dementia.

Materials and Methods

Participants

Ninety-seven participants of both sexes were included in this study, with 77.3% being women and 22.7% being men. The participants identified themselves as primary informal caregivers for individuals with dementia and their ages ranged from 20 to 72 years, with a mean age of 45.91 (± 13.37) years. On average, they provided 10.56 (± 8.33) hours of daily care to the person with dementia. The average weekly leisure hours for the caregiver are 8.12 (± 9.42). Among the sample, 61.9% are children of the person with dementia, 3.1% are siblings, 2.1% are sons-in-law, 5.2% are spouses, 6.2% are nephews/nieces, and 21.6% have another degree of relationship. Furthermore, 77.3% of caregivers provide multiple types of care (e.g., feeding, hygiene, shopping) to the person with dementia, while 22.7% are responsible for only one type of care. Regarding the gender distribution of individuals with dementia, 67% are female, and 33% are male. Most individuals with dementia are widows (61.9%) and have completed primary education (4 years of schooling) (42.3%). Additionally, 51.5% of individuals with dementia have a clinical diagnosis of Alzheimer's disease, 6.2% have vascular dementia, and 42.3% have other types of dementia (e.g., Parkinson's disease dementia, Lewy body dementia, and frontotemporal dementia). The patients have an average diagnosis time of 6.06 (± 5.99) years. Among them, 83.5% live with the caregiver, while 16.5% live alone. The inclusion criteria for caregivers in this study considered those who were responsible for patients with a clinical diagnosis of dementia.

Measures

As measurement instruments, a sociodemographic questionnaire was used to collect data from caregivers (age, hours of caregiving, etc.). The Big Five Inventory (Portuguese version by Brito-Costa et al., 2015) was employed to assess caregivers' personality across five dimensions through 44 items: Openness to Experience, Conscientiousness, Extroversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism. The instrument is rated on a Likert-type scale, with scores ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). Higher scores indicate a greater presence of these traits in the subjects. The internal consistency of the instrument yielded satisfactory values ($\alpha=0.78$). The social anxiety scale in social interaction contexts, comprising 19 items, and the social phobia scale, consisting of 20 items (Portuguese version by Pinto-Gouveia & Salvador, 2001), were employed. The first scale was utilized to assess caregivers' levels of social anxiety, while the second scale aimed to evaluate social phobia. The assessment of these instruments was based on a 4-point Likert-type scale, with higher scores indicating higher levels of social anxiety and social phobia. The psychometric characteristics of the scales were considered good, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.90 and good discriminant validity.

Procedure

In the initial phase, the representatives of informal caregiver support institutions were contacted. Once their

interest in participating and becoming acquainted with the study was expressed, working meetings were scheduled, during which the study's objectives were presented. With the collaboration of these institutions, family caregivers of individuals with dementia were subsequently approached. Those family caregivers who willingly agreed to participate in the study proceeded to sign an informed consent form, emphasizing the voluntary nature of their involvement, and assuring them of the absence of any health risks associated with their participation. The researchers made a commitment to adhere to all ethical and deontological responsibilities of the investigation, which were duly communicated to the participants. The study protocol was administered in a comfortable and well-lit room belonging to the collaborating institutions or through online tools, adapting the data collection method to the caregivers' availability.

Data Analysis

For the analysis of the collected data, the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, version 29 for Windows (IBM, SPSS Statistics 29) was used. Initially, the data were examined through descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages for categorical variables and means and standard deviations for numerical variables. The correlation between variables was assessed using the Pearson correlation coefficient, and statistical assumptions such as homogeneity of variance and normal distribution of the sample were checked. To investigate the predictive effect, both simple and multiple linear regression models were employed to estimate the magnitude and direction of the impact of independent variables on caregivers' personality dimensions. Only independent variables that demonstrated significant correlations with personality dimensions were included in the regression models. The assumptions of the regression models were also verified. A significance level of p -value < 0.05 was adopted to determine statistical significance.

Results

Correlation between Personality Traits, Caregiver's Age, Hours of Daily Care, Social Phobia, and Social Anxiety

The dimension of openness exhibits a significant negative relationship with hours of daily care ($r=-0.249$, $p=0.014$), a significant negative correlation with social phobia ($r=-0.276$, $p=0.006$), and a significant correlation with social anxiety ($r=-0.201$, $p=0.049$). However, no significant relationship was found between this dimension and caregiver's age ($r=0.018$, $p=0.861$). The dimension of conscientiousness exhibits a significant negative relationship with hours of daily care ($r=-0.257$, $p=0.011$). However, it does not show a statistically significant relationship with social phobia ($r=-0.050$, $p=0.625$), social anxiety ($r=-0.043$, $p=0.673$), nor caregiver's age ($r=-0.075$, $p=0.464$). The dimension of extraversion exhibits a significant negative relationship with hours of daily care ($r=-0.297$, $p=0.003$), social phobia ($r=-0.287$, $p=0.004$), and social anxiety ($r=-0.225$, $p=0.027$). However, this dimension does not

show a statistically significant relationship with caregiver's age ($r=0.050, p=0.626$). The dimension of agreeableness has a significant negative relationship with hours of daily care ($r=-0.209, p=0.040$). It does not have a statistically significant relationship with social phobia ($r=-0.082, p=0.426$), social anxiety ($r=-0.057, p=0.578$), nor caregiver's age ($r=0.101, p=0.323$). The dimension of neuroticism does not have a statistically significant relationship with hours of daily care ($r=-0.100, p=0.328$), social phobia ($r=0.124, p=0.228$),

social anxiety ($r=0.146, p=0.153$), nor caregiver's age ($r=0.092, p=0.371$).

Prediction of Personality Dimensions

The variables that previously correlated significantly with the personality dimensions were considered in the regression models. Table 1 represents the prediction effect using the simple linear regression model, and Table 2 shows the prediction effect using the multiple linear regression model.

Table 1

Prediction of Conscientiousness and Agreeableness

Regression models	B	SE	P
Conscientiousness			
Model 1 ($R^2=25.7\%$)			
Hours of daily care	-0.145	0.056	0.011*
Agreeableness			
Model 2 ($R^2=20.9\%$)			
Hours of daily care	-0.137	0.066	0.040*

Note. B – unstandardized Beta Coefficients; SE – standard error (unstandardized Coefficients); P – p-value (*0.05).

Table 2

Prediction Effects of Openness and Extraversion

Regression Models	B	SE	P
Openness			
Model 1 ($R^2=38.4\%$)			
Hours of daily care	-0.201	0.077	0.011*
Social phobia	-0.199	0.081	0.016*
Social anxiety	0.132	0.098	0.182
Extraversion			
Model 2 ($R^2=41.4\%$)			
Hours of daily care	-0.175	0.056	0.003*
Social phobia	-0.136	0.059	0.024*
Social anxiety	0.078	0.072	0.277

Note. B – unstandardized Beta Coefficients; SE – standard error (unstandardized Coefficients); P – p-value (*0.05).

Discussion

The aim of the study was to investigate whether characteristics such as social phobia, social anxiety, or hours of daily care could serve as predictors of personality dimensions in informal caregivers of individuals with dementia. Our results revealed that only social phobia and hours of daily care were significant variables in predicting Openness and Extraversion. Additionally, hours of daily care were also found to be predictors of Conscientiousness and Agreeableness among caregivers. Specifically, our findings revealed that the presence of social phobia negatively affects caregivers' openness to experience and extraversion. In fact, the presence of phobic characteristics, such as negative thoughts, negative self-images, or fear of failure, hinders individuals from understanding or accepting positive stimuli from others and circumstances (Calderón & Blázquez, 2014). Social phobia prevents them from arousing curiosity, a desire to enjoy new experiences and sensations, which are characteristic of openness to experience, or from exhibiting greater sociability, assertiveness, or a spirit of adventure, which characterize extraversion (Feixas, 2019; Pedroso de Lima

et al., 2014). However, individuals with higher levels of extraversion may demonstrate greater difficulties with attention and concentration on the tasks they must perform (Cloninger, 2013), which could have a negative influence on caregiving. Nevertheless, the negative effects caused by the presence of social phobia may vary depending on whether it is non-generalized social phobia, where the impact of this condition is less severe, or generalized social phobia with comorbidity with avoidant personality disorder, where problems are more pronounced and affect social interactions and the negative interpretation of received stimuli (Kessler, 2003). Our results also demonstrate that the number of hours spent in daily caregiving for individuals with dementia negatively affects caregivers' personality traits, namely their conscientiousness, agreeableness, openness to experience, and extraversion. According to the study by Tew et al. (2013), a longer duration of caregiving and a greater number of hours dedicated to caregiving harm caregivers' physical and mental health, social relationships, and environmental quality of life. A higher number of caregiving hours restricts individuals from engaging in new activities and having time to express

their ideas or creative freedom in other situations. The negative impact of caregiving hours on extraversion influences the sociability of individuals and reduces their energy in pursuing new challenges (Cloninger, 2013). On the other hand, when there is higher extraversion, individuals with dementia may benefit more from caregiving, as caregivers are more readily available to provide patients with new stimuli and activities that help delay the effects of cognitive deterioration caused by the disease (Norton et al., 2013), and enable them to positively express their emotions (Rabins et al., 1990). However, despite the study by Hajek & König (2018) finding a positive association between the number of hours informal caregivers dedicate to caregiving and conscientiousness, according to our results, we can infer that dedicating more hours to caregiving may compromise caregivers' levels of organization, planning, and even responsibility, which are characteristics of conscientiousness, as well as their levels of confidence, empathy, or cooperation, which characterize their agreeableness. The lack of empathy or cooperation with the care recipient can indeed exacerbate the difficulties experienced in caregiving (Hajek & König, 2018) and lead the caregiver to adopt maladaptive caregiving strategies.

Vugt et al. (2004) found that caregivers who devoted more than 90 hours per week to caregiving, when using maladaptive caregiving strategies, resulted in the patient showing more behavioral disturbances. However, it is through the expression of personal characteristics such as neuroticism that one would expect maladaptive caregiving strategies to be employed due to the caregiver's lack of understanding and acceptance of the patient's condition. Although our study did not reveal significant relationships with neuroticism, it is well-known that individuals who excessively focus on their fears or concerns tend to exhibit higher levels of neuroticism (Costa & McCrae, 2008), as greater neuroticism is indicative of higher emotional instability in individuals (Schultz & Schultz, 2021). As limitations, this study did not consider the personality characteristics of the patients and did not assess the impact that sexes or different age groups of caregivers might have on the results. However, this research contributes to the development of support guidelines for caregivers, highlighting the importance of such psychological factors and caregiving characteristics in personality functioning. It is crucial for informal caregiver support programs to address social phobia in order to minimize fears and enhance caregivers' interpersonal relationships. The construction of robust theoretical models based on these findings will also be essential.

Furthermore, additional studies are needed to understand how the effects of social phobia, social anxiety, and caregiving hours impact the personality of family caregivers over time and to identify significant differences concerning personal characteristics (e.g., degree of kinship) and clinical features of caregivers (e.g., comorbidity diagnoses) as well as the clinical characteristics of the patient (e.g., type of dementia or time of diagnosis).

Conclusions

Key conclusions to highlight include that social phobia demonstrates a significant impact on individuals who exhibit pronounced traits of personality encompassing Openness and Extraversion. Furthermore, an increased number of hours devoted to caring for individuals with dementia exerts a notable influence on individuals displaying evident traits of Conscientiousness, Agreeableness, Openness, and Extraversion that characterize their personality.

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Ethical Approval

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**SOCIAL AND
BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES**

Health Care Sciences

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Conceptualizing a Model for Cloud-Based Hospital Management Systems for the South African Public Health Sector

Authors' Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- C – Statistical analysis;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search;
- G – Funds collection

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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

Real-time access of information in the healthcare environment is essential, as it not only helps medical personnel to have adequate and timely information, but it also assists patients to be served more easily. Hospitals in rural areas are operating at a low bandwidth and have poor IT infrastructure that causes intermittent networks leading to disruptions and slow service delivery. This necessitates the Hospital Management System (HMS) to be deployed in the cloud environment to reduce the challenges leading to poor service delivery.

The aim of the study: to develop a model for cloud-based HMS for the South African public health sector.

Material and Methods:

This study identified three public district municipality hospitals in Gauteng Province, South Africa, that were already using HMS and used them for data collection. Each hospital had up to 50 healthcare workers, and this formed the population of 150 from the three hospitals, from which a sample size of 108 respondents was selected. Data were collected using a closed-ended questionnaire and analyzed quantitatively using SPSS v25.

Results:

The results demonstrated that the suggested model has a good prediction power of 60.9% ($R^2=0.609$) and that with the exception of environmental aspects, the rest of the constructs has a significant contribution to the successful implementation of the cloud-based HMS. Social aspects had the highest prediction power of 60.0% ($\beta=0.600$) at $p=0.001$; followed by risk analysis and control with 41.3% ($\beta=0.413$) at $p=0.009$. On the other hand, environmental aspects had the least and non-significant prediction of 12.3%.

Conclusions:

This study contributes to the ongoing call to have seamless healthcare provision systems. The model developed in this study extends the research of modernizing healthcare provision by leveraging technological innovations.

Keywords:
Copyright:

cloud computing, hospital management systems, healthcare, public, South Africa
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Introduction

Information and communication technology (ICT) is universally regarded as a vital tool for improving business competitiveness and economic growth of a country as it has the potential to improve the quality, safety, and efficiency of service delivery. Generally, there is a consensus that ICT has significant effects on the productivity of firms, but these effects can only be realized if, and when, ICTs are widely spread and used efficiently.

ICT has the ability to help people collect, store, manage, and distribute knowledge. For instance, in the healthcare domain the use of information technology (IT) has improved communication between medical personnel and patients (Djock, 2023). Previously, patients would queue for hours to get help in hospitals as everything was done manually. This trend has, however, changed with the increasing use of automated healthcare systems such as Hospital Management Systems (HMS) that have increased the speed at which patients' information is accessed and retrieved (Khan et al., 2014). The use of IT and its application has propelled developments that have improved service delivery in all sectors, inclusive of public health. Recent developments in remote healthcare systems have witnessed significant interest from the IT industry, which provides universal and easily deployable healthcare systems (Djock, 2023; Profetto et al., 2022).

Katuu (2018) asserts that well-formed hospital management workflows involve important decision-making that should be done efficiently and quickly. Katuu (2018) indicates that it is becoming difficult in many health sector facilities to improve efficiency without the use of HMS. The HMS assists in the handling of the different directions of hospital workflows, and it helps in managing smooth healthcare performance along with administrative, medical, legal, and financial control (Djock, 2023). Further still, HMS is essential in managing automated operations of the hospital, using radio frequency identification (RFID) tags to secure access (Profetto et al., 2022).

The aim of the study. To develop a model that informs the deployment of the Hospital Management Systems within the cloud.

To realize the research goal, the following objectives were set to be achieved: to determine factors that influence cloud-based HMS implementation, to determine the extent of cloud-based HMS integration in the South African health institutions and also rank and use the identified factors for the development of a cloud-based HMS model for the South African health sector.

Materials and Methods

This study followed a quantitative research approach. The study used close-ended questionnaires to collect data. Due to increased restrictions of visitations at many institutions, data was collected online. The questionnaire with close-ended questions was uploaded onto Survey Monkey and the link leading to the survey was sent to the contact person to distribute to the respondents. At each hospital, the researcher got a

contact person, mostly from the ICT directorate. For anonymity, the questionnaire on the Survey Monkey was designed in such a way that respondents only needed to click on the submission button and the filled questionnaire was captured on Survey Monkey database with the respondents' particulars on completion of the questionnaire, the filled datasets were exported to the Statistical Package for Social Scientists (SPSS v25) for analysis. The questionnaire was designed in such a way that neither the particulars of the individual respondents nor those of the health institution were asked, so anonymity was ensured. After data had been captured on the Survey Monkey database, the questionnaire was exported to SPSS. However, for easy analysis the questionnaire was coded in such a way that the constructs and their attributes are shorted to carry meaning while observing originality of the question item and the construct.

The population of this study was health personnel in public hospitals that are using HMS in Gauteng Province, South Africa. This study identified three public hospitals that were already using HMS. According to Massyn et al.'s (2020) report, South African hospitals are human resource constrained and on average, there are between 30 to 50 medical personnel and health workers in district hospitals and slightly more numbers in provincial hospitals. Hence, the population of the study based on the district hospital level was 150 respondents.

By using the Krejcie and Morgan's tool for determining the sample size of a finite population, the derived sample size for this study was 108. Based on this sample size, a total of 130 survey links were distributed and out of this 98 completed questionnaires were returned though 83 were usable.

Research is conducted to collect relevant information that can be used to solve the identified research problem (Babbie, 2016). Hence, a high level of reliability and validity should be maintained when collecting data. Additionally, the measuring instrument must be designed such that it consistently measures what it is supposed to measure, and research should ensure that while collecting data, the obtained results are trustworthy in order to develop future forecasts (Yin, 2014). Research standards are based on credibility, reliability, and conformity of data hence validity and reliability must be ensured for the quality and research standards.

Reliability refers to the measuring instrument's capacity to produce similar results with duplicated or replicated tests (Yin, 2014).

This study used the Cronbach's alpha also known as alpha co-efficient to determine the reliability or internal consistence of the questionnaire and its constructs. The overall reliability of the questionnaire with 32 items as demonstrated in Table 1 was found to be 0.960, which reliability was considered good since it was above the recommended threshold of 0.7, and also comparing the number of items in the questionnaire (Heale & Twycross, 2015).

Table 1
 Overall Reliability Statistics of the Measuring Instrument

Reliability statistics		
Cronbach's alpha	Cronbach's alpha based on standardized items	Number of items
0.960	0.960	32

Results

The set of hypotheses were evaluated using regression analysis, with the findings being reported. The statistical analysis of the data were performed using SPSS 25.0.

Table 2
 Frequencies of Participants' Demographics

Factors	Items	Frequency		
		People (n)	Percentage (%)	Cumulative percentage (%)
Age	21-30 years	27	32.5	32.5
	31-40 years	36	43.4	75.9
	41-50 years	20	24.1	100.0
	Total	83	100.0	100.0
Level of education	Grade 12 and below	6	7.2	7.2
	Diploma	24	28.9	36.1
	Advanced diploma	7	8.4	44.5
	Degree	27	32.5	77.0
	Post Graduate	19	22.9	100.0
Experience	Total	83	100.0	100.0
	0-5 years	38	45.8	45.8
	6-10 years	26	31.3	77.1
	11-15 years	7	8.4	85.5
	16-20 years	3	3.6	89.1
	21-25 years	3	3.6	92.7
	26 years and above	6	7.2	100.0
Job position	Total	83	100.0	100.0
	Administrator	13	15.7	15.7
	Cleaner	5	6.0	21.7
	Doctor	8	9.6	31.3
	Driver	1	1.2	32.5
	Filing Assistant	1	1.2	33.7
	Lab Assistant	1	1.2	34.9
	Matron	2	2.4	37.3
	Nurse	41	49.4	86.7
	Porter	2	2.4	89.2
	Surgeon	9	10.8	100.0
Cloud computing	Total	83	100.0	100.0
	No	16	19.3	19.3
	Yes	67	80.7	100.0

As demonstrated in Table 2, over 67.5% (n=56) of the respondents were above the age of 30 years. These respondents had a good level of education with only 28.9% (n=24) having an education level of a diploma. The implication of these findings is that such respondents could make a good decision about the asked question that improved the validity of the results obtained for this study. The respondents' level of education is presented graphically (Figure 1).

According to Cohen et al. (2018), a significance level of 0.05 is regarded as acceptable. By providing a relationship between the variables that could be used to predict the values of the independent variables. The findings demonstrated in Table 1 show that all the hypothesized relationships were accepted, with the exception of environmental aspects in order to develop the final research model. The population of the study based on the district hospital level was 150 respondents. Age, level of education, work experience, job position and cloud awareness were the different demographic and situational variables that were identified as being relevant for this study. Participant's demographics are shown in Table 2, which is broken down into the relevant categories..

The age as a demographic variable has been found by other researchers (Kalema, 2013; Venkatesh et al., 2012) to be a good predicting factor in the studies of technological innovation implementation. This implies that in terms of migrating HMS in the cloud-based environment, mature individuals are more responsible in observing controls and measures, security rules as well as guidelines. Consequently, this also implies that the questionnaire was answered by responsible people within the healthcare facilities.

Figure 1
 Respondents' Level of Education

It is also demonstrated in Table 2 that 15.7% (n=13) of contributions to this study were from hospital administrators, 7.0% (n=5) were from cleaners, doctors contributed 9.6% (n=8), drivers, filling assistants, and lab assistants each contributed 1.2% (n=1). A contribution of 2.4% (n=2) was from matrons, nurses contributed 49.4% (n=41), porters 2.4% (n=2) and surgeons contributed 10.8% (n=9). Relevance of the job title as well as seniority plays an important role in maintaining data integrity that leads to better decision-making. The role of an individual's position within an organization has been identified in various technological innovation based studies as being critical and having high interacting effects on the overall prediction of models explaining technology acceptance and use (Kalema, 2013; Rahim et al., 2022; Venkatesh et al., 2012).

Results demonstrated in Table 2 indicate that 45.8% (n=38) of the participants have at least 5 years of work

experience, 31.3% (n=26) have between 6 and 10 years, 8.4% (n=7) have between 11 and 15 years, 3.6% (n=3) have between 16 and 20 years, 3.6% (n=3) have between 21 and 25 years, and 7.2% (n=6) have more than 26 years. Experience places an individual in a position of responsibility, source of knowledge and wisdom as one with a good experience within an organization is considered a master of processes and operations. Previous researchers (Tripathi, 2018; Williams et al., 2016) note that individuals with good experience are considered as the knowledge base of the organization. This implies that since a good number of respondents of this study (54.2% or n=45) had experience of 6 years and above, it signifies that data for this study was collected from the "knowledge base" of the hospitals' financial institutions. The work experience of the respondents is presented graphically (Figure 2).

Figure 2
 Overall Working Experience

Respondents were also asked to show the awareness of the cloud environment. Results indicated that 80.7% (n=67) of the participants had knowledge or were aware of the cloud whereas 19.3% (n=16) indicated that they were not aware of the cloud computing concept. When users are aware of a technological innovation, its implementation becomes less complicated as little sensitization will be needed during the implementation process.

Regression Analysis

Further to descriptive analysis, a regression analysis was conducted to determine the prediction of the overall model as well as how much each independent variable contribute to the overall prediction of the model. The model was found to have a good prediction power of 60.9% ($R^2=0.609$). The prediction contribution for each independent variable is illustrated in the results of regression analysis (Table 3).

Table 3
 Regression Coefficients*

Model	Unstandardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	0.359	0.062	-	5.790	0.000	-	-
TechChar	0.429	0.218	0.139	1.967	0.042	0.257	3.889
CloudComRead	0.407	0.148	0.256	2.756	0.023	0.370	2.701
OrgAsp	0.759	0.214	0.284	3.549	0.016	0.234	4.272
EnvtAsp	-0.136	0.205	-0.123	-.664	0.509	0.228	4.387
IndChar	0.595	0.195	0.182	3.051	0.017	0.263	3.803
RiskAnCtrl	0.487	0.182	0.413	2.681	0.009	0.331	3.018
SocAsp	-0.701	0.193	-0.600	-3.632	0.001	0.289	3.458

Note. *Dependent variable – cloud-based Hospital Management System.

Results demonstrated in Table 3 indicate that with the exception of environmental aspects, the rest of the constructs showed a significant contribution to the successful implementation of a cloud-based HMS. Social aspects had the highest contribution with the prediction power of 60.0% ($\beta=0.600$) at $p=0.001$; followed by risk analysis and control with a prediction power of 41.3% ($\beta=0.413$) at $p=0.009$. On the other hand, environmental aspects' contribution of 12.3% at $p=0.509$ was relatively high, it was found not to be significant.

Table 3 also measured the existence of multi collinearity by using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). The rule of thumb indicates that for multicollinearity collinearity to exist, the value of $VIF > 10$. However, as indicated in Table 3, all the VIF values were less than 5, which indicated that multicollinearity does not exist.

Based on the findings, the conceptualized model for cloud-based Hospital Management Systems for the South African public health sector was derived as demonstrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3
 Model for Cloud-Based Hospital Management System

*Note. TOE – Technology-Organization-Environment framework.

Discussion

Based on the results of the study, the implications of the significance of the variables demonstrated in Figure 3 should be explained.

The Technology-Organization-Environment model developed by De Pietro et al. (1990) underpinned the development of the cloud-based Hospital Management Systems.

Technological factors

The implication of this finding is that on average there have been challenges of inadequate health institutions and shortage of healthcare human resource in many developing countries, especially those in Sub-Saharan Africa (Kalema & Busobozi, 2020). Hence, technology and its innovations are seen as one way to bridge the gap of resource constraint by providing remote access capabilities to healthcare resources. The significance of this variable confirms the fact that citizens appreciate the value and contribution of technology towards healthcare provision and such good and available technology will boost the migration of HMS to the cloud environment. On the other hand, technological aspects are perceived to be a major part of cloud technology and a basis for the cloud to change the computing process from using the HMS as stand-alone systems to a networked system that solves the challenges of accessibility and governance, especially in resource-constrained organizations like hospitals. The finding of this study is in agreement with those of previous researchers (Idoga et al., 2019; Sadoughi et al., 2020) who also stated that regardless of how technology is looked at as either top-down or bottom-up; its role for cloud migration is enormous.

Organizational factors

The significance of this variable implies that organizational aspects that entail factors like top management support, budgets and finances, employees' empowerment for knowledge creation through trainings, policies and standards, organizational size and structure, measures for collaboration and knowledge sharing, as well as enhanced business processes play an essential role in the migration of services and applications to the cloud. The findings of this study concur with those of many previous others on the migration to the cloud that have found organization aspects to have a stronger significant influence (Alipour et al., 2021; Idoga et al., 2018; Sadoughi et al., 2020).

Environmental aspects

Environment aspects have been found in various healthcare research of developing countries to be significant, yet they were found not to be significant in this study (Kalema & Busobozi, 2020; Maphumulo & Bhengu, 2019). The implication of this finding is that when services are migrated to the cloud the issue of environment is overshadowed by the organizational aspects. For instance, services will be migrated to the cloud that might reside in a different country or continent and such migration requires more organizational support than the environment characteristics. With good support from the organizational top management in terms of budgets, training of users, employing the right staff, signing good service level agreements with vendors to

assist with configuration management, provisioning required tools, assisting with log collections, patching systems and ticketing systems, cloud-based activities may have little hindrance as compared to the on-premises IT facilities.

Individual characteristics

Individual characteristics have been found in much previous research of technological innovation adoption, implementation and use to be significant (Adler-Milstein et al., 2015; Kalema & Busobozi, 2020). The implication of these findings is that individual characteristics like attitude and beliefs, perceptions, training, and education are crucial for cloud migration because when services are migrated the success of the administrative tasks will depend on the capabilities of the individuals to manage both the migration processes and the operation. Another factor to consider is that migration of a Hospital Information System (HIS) to the cloud comes with several advantages for both healthcare providers and patients in terms of quality service delivery and cost-efficient solutions to the patients, as well as having seamless collaborations among healthcare facilities. These findings concur with those of other researchers (Idoga et al., 2019; Singh et al., 2022) who also noted that cloud-based hospital systems support collaborations that bring efficient data exchange with fast feedback for the patients through information sharing, but such could only be achieved if individuals using the systems have the capabilities and positive perceptions towards the system.

Social aspects

The significance of this variable implies that cloud migration has a high dependence on information sharing due to its potential to provide remote access to data. The social interaction could be either internal or external and as such supports information sharing and unrestricted flow of information in the cloud-based health system, which leads to effectiveness. Internal social aspects include influence of others to accept, and believe and trust in the system; while the external is related to external collaboration when the system is migrated and support during the use of the system. The findings of this study support those of previous researchers such as (Venkatesh et al., 2012; Walker & Walker, 2022) who noted that social aspects play an essential role in voluntary technological innovation implementation, adoption, and use.

Risk analysis and control

The significance of this variable confirms the fact that risk awareness starts with identifying and reporting near accidents, incidents, complaints, or other undesirable situations that could be the order of the day in the cloud environment. This implies that risk management in the cloud should embrace a flexible software platform that can record and detail the data and its operations, direct follow up of workflow automation tools, carry out analysis of trends of root causes of risks and associated challenges, manage dashboards to monitor information, as well as monitor improvement actions. The findings of this study concur with those of other researchers (Alipour et al., 2021; Maphumulo & Bhengu, 2019; Rahman et al., 2017; Singh et al., 2022) who also observed that

managing risks associated with HIS is paramount in assuring patients' safety regardless of hospital size and structure. Hence, risk management and control is a significant factor for migrating HIS to the cloud and healthcare systems should be mindful of the techniques that they use to migrate their services.

Cloud-based services migration has many implications, such as budgets and costs to technical aspects including maintenance and delivery. This implies that to get a vivid understanding and generalization of findings for the migration of HIS to the cloud environment, this study needed to involve as many stakeholders as possible who interact with the system. However, because this study collected online data, some stakeholders could not participate in the study for one reason or the other. More so, this study also needed to triangulate the methods during data collection whereby some data would have been collected qualitatively from policy makers, like top hospital administrators, through interviews. This study, therefore, recommends that future research should increase the scope of data collection by increasing the number of participating hospitals in the study and try to triangulate the methods by using a combination of quantitative and qualitative data collection methods, such as interviewing policy and strategic decision makers.

For conclusiveness of a cloud-based HIS, one needs to do a follow up of what happens after migration. This could also be in the form of observing the adherence to policies and standards as well as assessment of the reduction in the total cost of ownership of the system after migration. Therefore, since a cross-sectional data collection approach was used, this study recommends that a longitudinal research data collection should be used by future researchers in order to be in an actual position to report what will happen after some time. A longitudinal survey will also assist in determining whether medical personnel and healthcare workers are effectively using the system.

Several researchers (Kalema, 2013; Rahim et al., 2022; Tripathi, 2018) note that users of technology may have their perceptions change with time. This implies that analysis of users' demographics and situational variables should go beyond descriptive and analyse the moderating and interacting effects of these variables in order to make a better prediction of what happens after some time interval. Much as this study appreciates this observation, respondent's demographics and situational variables were only analysed using descriptive analysis to show the frequencies. This may cause a limitation in predicting future occurrences in the usage of the cloud services. This study recommends that future research should make effort to analyse the interacting effects of the moderating factors.

Conclusions

Migrating services and applications to the cloud is a big step. However, it is the first step as migration is one thing and administering the use of the migrated services is another. A successful cloud-based HIS requires the healthcare system to remain active and vigilant, hence the need to train all stakeholders to achieve advanced skills

that will enable them to use these migrated services. As emphasized by Sadoughi et al. (2020), keeping and maintaining cloud security is a pain-staking task that needs any organization to remain abreast with technological developments, and to be many steps ahead of its adversaries. Cloud migration complacency may be limiting in informing a successful cloud strategy; hence, organizations need to have constant evaluation of what their IT support team can do better and how such can be achieved.

This study revealed that organizational, technological, individual, and social aspects as well as risk control and analysis are important determinants in shaping the perspective of cloud-based HIS users. However, the cloud-based system characteristics such as ease-of-use, relative advantage, scalability, security, and trust are major antecedents in accepting a cloud-based HIS. This implies that an organization needs to simplify the understanding and use of the cloud by users by enhancing their capabilities through training as well as involving them in the decision-making process around the migration to the cloud.

As observed by recent researchers (Abbas et al., 2020; Kalema, 2022; Singh et al., 2022) in the current era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR), the greatest opportunities as well as the greatest threats are the new trends in computing. This technology "Big Bang" has and is continuously changing the landscape of every organization, including those in the healthcare sector. Migrating services to the cloud is increasingly becoming the order of the day for those organizations seeking agility. Since such has made the cloud to move faster, the earlier organizations gain diversified expertise in using and administering services in this environment the better is their future survival. As a result, the model designed for this study could be a beneficial guide to empirical research on cloud-based systems, not only for the healthcare sector but also for other sectors. The findings of this study are intended to help healthcare decision-makers by increasing their awareness of the cloud-based systems, and to keep in mind the impact of the identified factors on decision-making at all levels within healthcare.

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Ethical Approval

The study obtained ethical clearance from the institution Ethics Committee (Ref. No. FCRE/ICT/2021/06/002(1).

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LETTER TO THE EDITOR

LETTERS TO THE EDITOR

LETTER TO THE EDITOR

How Much Do We Need – What is the Limitation of Wants and Where Do We End Up with Unfulfilled Desires?

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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

The paper considers the significance of recognizing the limitations of our wants and the consequences of unfulfilled desires. It should be emphasized that an unchecked pursuit of endless wants leads to unhappiness, unhealthiness, and selfishness, ultimately contributing to social disorder. In a society driven by consumerism and materialism, individuals often find themselves trapped in an endless cycle of desires and wants. However, understanding the limitations of these wants is crucial for personal well-being and social harmony.

When our desires become insatiable and unattainable, we experience a constant sense of dissatisfaction and unhappiness. The relentless pursuit of material possessions and external validation results in a shallow and unfulfilled existence. The relentless pursuit of personal desires often leads to neglecting our physical and mental well-being. Unhealthy habits and lifestyle choices emerge as we prioritize immediate gratification over long-term health and happiness.

The selfish nature of unfulfilled desires manifests as individuals prioritize their own needs and wants above the well-being of others. This self-centeredness erodes empathy, cooperation, and social cohesion, ultimately contributing to social disorder and unrest. Recognizing the limitations of our wants and cultivating contentment and gratitude is vital for personal fulfillment and social harmony. By embracing a mindset of sufficiency and focusing on meaningful connections and experiences, individuals can break free from the cycle of unfulfilled desires. This shift in perspective promotes personal happiness, healthier lifestyles, and the cultivation of a more compassionate and inclusive society.

Conclusions:

Understanding the limitations of our wants and recognizing the consequences of unfulfilled desires is crucial for personal and societal well-being. By striving for contentment, practicing gratitude, and prioritizing genuine connections over material possessions, we can foster a more balanced and harmonious society, free from the unhappiness, unhealthiness, and selfishness that arise from unchecked desires.

Keywords:

limitation of wants, unfulfilled desires, social harmony, insatiable, unattainable, unhealthy habits, immediate gratification

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Dear Editor,

Our wants and desires are unlimited, non-archival, and have no boundaries. Understanding wants and unlimited desires is a complex one that has been explored by philosophers and economists for centuries. At its core, I argue that human wants are unlimited, while the resources available to satisfy those wants are limited. This creates a fundamental tension in human society, as we are constantly striving to satisfy our desires, but we are never able to do so completely.

Unlimited desires revolve around the nature of human desires and the implications they have on our lives. It raises questions about the extent of our needs, the limitations of our wants, and the consequences of unfulfilled desires. Human wants are inherent aspects of our nature, encompassing various material, emotional, and social desires. These wants arise from our innate needs for survival, comfort, security, and fulfillment. However, the challenge arises when our wants extend beyond what is necessary for our well-being and become insatiable or limitless.

While it is important to acknowledge and address our genuine needs, unlimited desires refer to the relentless pursuit of wants without considering their practicality, sustainability, or impact on ourselves and others. In my opinion, one often exceeds what is reasonable or necessary for a fulfilling life.

Understanding the limitations of our wants is a critical aspect of personal growth and contentment. It involves recognizing the difference between needs and wants, evaluating the true value and significance of our desires, and discerning the long-term consequences of pursuing them without moderation. Unfulfilled desires can lead to a perpetual sense of dissatisfaction and restlessness. When we constantly chase after wants that are beyond our reach or inherently unattainable, we may find ourselves caught in a cycle of striving, discontent, and disappointment. This can negatively impact our overall well-being, relationships, and sense of fulfillment.

To remain happy, it is important to accept limitations. Recognizing and accepting the limitations of our wants can bring a sense of clarity and freedom. It allows us to prioritize our genuine needs, focus on meaningful experiences and relationships, and cultivate contentment within ourselves. By developing a mindful approach to desires and embracing a sense of sufficiency, we can find a balance between pursuing our aspirations and appreciating the present moment. Understanding the root of wants and desires prompts us to reflect on our motivations, priorities, and the potential consequences of our actions. By cultivating self-awareness, practicing moderation, and embracing gratitude, we can navigate the complexities of desires and lead a more fulfilling and balanced life.

Defining wants. There are several different ways to define wants and desires. Some scholars define wants as those things that we need to survive, while others define them as those things that we simply want, but do not need (Dierksmeier, 2014). Still, others define wants as a combination of both needs and desires. The limitation of wants is a matter of debate. Some of us argue that there

is no limit to human wants, while others argue that there are certain basic needs that all humans have and that these needs can be satisfied (Desmarais-Tremblay, 2017). When our wants are unfulfilled, we can experience several negative emotions, such as frustration, anger, and anxiety. We may also become materialistic, constantly striving to acquire more and more possessions in an attempt to satisfy our desires. In some cases, unfulfilled wants can lead to destructive behavior, such as addiction or crime.

There are several different ways to deal with unfulfilled wants. Some people try to suppress their desires, while others try to find ways to satisfy them healthily. Some people also find that it is helpful to focus on the things that they do have, rather than the things that they do not have.

Our wants are shaped by our culture, our upbringing, and our individual experiences.

Our wants are influenced by various factors such as culture, upbringing, and personal experiences. These influences shape our desires and play a significant role in determining what we perceive as necessary or valuable. However, it is crucial to recognize that we have the power to shape and control our wants, rather than being solely driven by external forces.

Curbing our wants can be a transformative practice that allows us to find inner peace and contribute to fostering peace in our interactions with others. By consciously examining our desires and questioning their true significance, we can separate genuine needs from superficial wants. This introspective process helps us develop a sense of discernment and prioritize what truly aligns with our values and well-being.

By cultivating contentment and embracing a mindset of sufficiency, we can find peace within ourselves. This involves appreciating the present moment, expressing gratitude for what we have, and recognizing that fulfillment does not solely rely on external acquisitions. It is about finding joy in the simple pleasures of life and nurturing meaningful connections with others. When we can curb our wants and find peace within ourselves, we are better equipped to help others and contribute to fostering peace in our communities. By shifting our focus from individualistic pursuits to collective well-being, we can extend compassion, empathy, and support to those around us. Through acts of kindness, understanding, and cooperation, we contribute to creating a harmonious and peaceful environment for everyone (Bhandari, 2023b).

Curbing our wants is a transformative process that involves questioning and shaping our desires in alignment with our values. By finding inner peace and contentment, we can extend that energy to others, fostering peace in our interactions and relationships. Through conscious choices, gratitude, and acts of compassion, we can contribute to a more peaceful world (Bhandari, 2023a):

- Our wants can be both positive and negative. They can motivate us to achieve great things, but they can also lead us to make poor decisions.

- It is important to be aware of our wants and to manage them healthily.

- We should not let our wants control us. We should instead focus on living a life that is meaningful and fulfilling.

Desires, wants and dissatisfaction are very complex processes. Desires, want, and dissatisfaction is a complex process influenced by various psychological, social, and cultural factors. Understanding this complexity requires delving into several key aspects:

1. Formation of desires: Desires can emerge from a variety of sources, including innate biological needs, social conditioning, personal experiences, and cultural influences. Our desires are shaped by the values, beliefs, and expectations ingrained in us through upbringing and societal norms.

2. Subjectivity of wants: Wants are subjective and vary from person to person. What one individual desires may differ from another based on their unique perspectives, personalities, and life experiences. This subjectivity adds to the complexity of understanding desires and their fulfillment.

3. Hedonic treadmill: The phenomenon known as the "hedonic treadmill" (Brickman & Campbell, 1971) suggests that humans tend to adapt quickly to new circumstances and experiences. As a result, even when desires are fulfilled, the initial happiness and satisfaction may fade, leading to new desires and an ongoing cycle of seeking more to maintain a sense of fulfillment (Rosenbloom, 2010, August 7).

The hedonic treadmill, also known as hedonic adaptation, is a psychological phenomenon that refers to the tendency of individuals to return to a relatively stable level of happiness or well-being after experiencing positive or negative life events. It suggests that despite changes in circumstances or material possessions, people's happiness levels tend to revert to a baseline or set point.

According to the hedonic treadmill theory, individuals initially experience a boost in happiness when they achieve or acquire something they desire, such as a promotion, a new possession, or a positive life event. However, over time, this initial increase in happiness diminishes, and individuals adapt to their new circumstances. As a result, they require even more positive events or acquisitions to maintain the same level of happiness.

The concept of the hedonic treadmill is rooted in the idea that humans have a remarkable capacity to adjust to changing circumstances, both positive and negative, and return to their baseline level of happiness. This adaptation can occur relatively quickly, which may explain why the initial excitement or satisfaction derived from achieving a desire tends to fade over time.

The hedonic treadmill has implications for our understanding of happiness and well-being. It suggests that the pursuit of material possessions or external achievements alone may not lead to long-term happiness. Instead, it highlights the importance of focusing on internal factors, personal growth and cultivating a positive mindset to sustain well-being.

By recognizing the hedonic treadmill, individuals can become more mindful of their desires and aspirations. They can strive to find happiness in experiences, relationships, personal development, and meaningful connections rather than relying solely on external factors that may provide temporary satisfaction.

The Hedonic treadmill encourages individuals to seek a more balanced and sustainable approach to happiness, one that acknowledges the transience of external desires and focuses on cultivating inner contentment and well-being.

4. Social comparison: Social comparison plays a significant role in the psychology of desires, which can lead to negative emotions such as envy, jealousy, and discontentment. We often evaluate our desires and satisfaction based on how we perceive others' possessions, achievements, or lifestyles. This comparison can lead to feelings of dissatisfaction if we believe our desires are not met in comparison to others.

When we compare ourselves to others, particularly in terms of possessions, achievements, or social status, we often overlook or devalue what we already have. This tendency to focus on what we lack rather than appreciating our circumstances can generate feelings of inadequacy and fuel an unending cycle of desires and dissatisfaction.

Finding peace and contentment requires a shift in mindset and a conscious effort to let go of the habit of comparison. It involves cultivating a sense of gratitude for what we have and embracing the idea that our worth and happiness are not defined by external markers or comparisons with others.

Understanding our motives and choices is crucial in determining how much we truly need and setting limitations on our wants. By reflecting on our values, priorities, and genuine needs, we can develop a clearer understanding of what brings true fulfillment to our lives. It is important to distinguish between genuine needs and desires fueled by external influences or societal pressures.

Choosing to be happy and satisfied with what we have, while also striving for personal growth and improvement, can lead to a more peaceful and contented life. We focusing on our progress and setting goals that align with our values, we can free ourselves from the constant cycle of comparison and find fulfillment in our unique journey. Finding peace and contentment requires a shift in mindset, letting go of comparison, embracing gratitude, and focusing on our personal growth and happiness without being overly influenced by external standards.

It is a continuous process that requires self-reflection, self-acceptance, and an appreciation for the present moment.

5. Impact of advertising and consumer culture: Advertising and consumer culture heavily influence our desires by promoting certain products, lifestyles, and ideals. These external influences shape our perceptions of what is desirable and can contribute to a perpetual sense of dissatisfaction as we constantly strive to attain the advertised standards of happiness and success.

6. Psychological needs: Our desires are often connected to deeper psychological needs, such as the need for belonging, autonomy, competence, and self-actualization. Unfulfilled psychological needs can lead to a sense of dissatisfaction, prompting us to seek fulfillment through various wants and desires.

7. Mindfulness and contentment: Developing mindfulness and cultivating contentment can help navigate the complexity of desires and dissatisfaction. Mindfulness practices enable us to observe our desires without judgment, understand their transient nature, and develop a sense of contentment by appreciating the present moment and cultivating gratitude.

I think desires, wants, and dissatisfaction are a multifaceted process influenced by a range of psychological, social, and cultural factors. Recognizing the complexity of this process allows us to develop a deeper understanding of our desires and work towards finding a sense of contentment and fulfillment in our lives.

Conclusions

The question of how much we need, and the limitations of our wants is a complex and deeply personal one. Our wants, influenced by various factors such as culture, society, and personal experiences, can shape our desires and aspirations. While wants can serve as motivators for personal growth and achievement, they can also lead us astray if driven by external pressures or misguided values. It is important to recognize that unfulfilled desires can have both positive and negative consequences. On one hand, they can inspire us to strive for more, push our boundaries, and achieve great things. On the other hand, unchecked desires can result in a perpetual cycle of dissatisfaction, comparison, and a constant yearning for more without finding true contentment.

Finding a balance between our wants and needs is crucial. This involves introspection, self-awareness, and aligning our desires with our values and long-term well-being. It requires us to differentiate between genuine needs and superficial wants and to cultivate gratitude for what we already have.

Understanding our motives and choices is essential in determining the extent of our wants and setting meaningful limitations. By focusing on personal growth, pursuing goals that align with our values, and being mindful of the potential consequences of unfulfilled desires, we can strive for a more fulfilling and contented life. Ultimately, finding contentment lies in the ability to appreciate and be grateful for the present moment, while

also working towards personal growth and improvement. It is a journey of self-discovery and self-acceptance, where we learn to find peace and fulfillment within ourselves rather than constantly comparing ourselves to others or seeking external validation. By recognizing the limitations of our wants, embracing gratitude, and aligning our desires with our authentic selves, we can navigate the complexities of unfulfilled desires and find a path that leads to genuine contentment and a sense of inner peace.

Ethical Approval

The study protocol was consistent with the ethical guidelines of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki as reflected in a prior approval by the Institution's Human Research Committee.

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LETTERS TO THE EDITOR

LETTER TO THE EDITOR

Human and Artificial Intelligence Interaction

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Background and Aim of Study:

Abstract

The advent of artificial intelligence (AI) has changed our world forever. No matter what it is that we do, there will always be a place for AI in what we do. Controlling and managing this system of interactions is still within our power. However, the potential and the speed of developing AI-based information technology is so great that we may soon need to concede this primacy.

The aim of the study: to justify whether artificial intelligence will become our assistant or, on the contrary, create problems; to identify what needs to be done to build a harmonious Human-AI System of interactions and relationships.

Conclusions:

It requires the development, ratification and implementation of laws that regulate the norms of interactions and relationships between humans and AI. The first steps have already been taken to legitimise AI-based Chatbots in scientific research and publications. This paper offers an attribution for a product created by humans without the involvement of AI – "AI Free. Human Created". The use of this attribution helps to protect the individual's right to freedom of choice and work.

Keywords:

Human-AI System, interaction, relationship, artificial intelligence, ChatBot, attribution, "AI Free. Human Created"

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Dear Editor,

Our entire civilisation, the achievements of science and culture, have been created by human intelligence. However, we now have artificial intelligence (AI) that could be its alternative. This situation has actualised some of the most important questions about the relationship between human intelligence and artificial intelligence. Firstly, will AI help us or, on the contrary, create problems? Secondly, what do we need to do to create a harmonious system of interacting and relating? Human civilisation has entered a new spiral of development in the age of information technology where, with the advent of AI, a new "Human-AI System" of

relationships has emerged. The authors (Melnyk & Pypenko, 2023) have offered the essence of the definition "Human-AI System". This allows us to clarify the essential features of the new phenomenon under consideration, which opens prospects for its further study.

First of all, we should accept as axiomatic the idea that our world has been changed forever with the advent of AI. Whatever we do, there will always be a place for AI in what we do. And the role of AI in our lives will continue to grow. It is still within our power to control and manage this system of interactions. However, the

potential and the speed of development of AI-based information technologies are so great that we may have to concede this primacy in the near future.

It has been less than a year (30 November 2022) since the launch of ChatGPT. ChatGPT is an AI-based conversational Large Language Model (LLM). The potential applications of LLMs in research and practice look promising, given their ability to generate creative responses.

In the first 3 months of its existence, ChatGPT has become an indispensable tool for 100 million people worldwide. A large number of people of different ages and social statuses, from schoolchildren to university professors, have found ChatGPT to be an indispensable tool for dealing with issues in their personal and professional lives.

This popularity makes ChatGPT an obvious positive answer to the question of whether AI has become our assistant. We are sure that there will be millions of schoolchildren and students who actively use ChatGPT for their studies and for solving tasks assigned to them in educational institutions. At the same time, it is very likely that millions of teachers and university professors are also using AI to prepare assignments for these students. This creates a paradoxical situation in which the AI becomes both the object and the subject of action (writing and solving its own tasks).

The other question is whether this is a problem or not. As in the first case, we believe that the answer to this question will be in the affirmative. Undoubtedly, replacing one's own opinion and efforts in solving tasks with an AI answer will have a negative impact on students' personal cognitive sphere (intelligence) and competence level.

To be fair, we should point out that this is a problem for the faculty as well. Over the past year, there has been a significant increase in the number of research studies, and therefore articles, using AI-based tools. Previous studies have addressed the legitimacy of using AI in scientific research and publications (Melnyk & Pypenko, 2023), and the dilemma of quality versus quantity of scientific publications, which will become particularly relevant with the advent of AI (Melnyk & Pypenko, 2021). Discussions about the tendency to replace humans with AI, and the potential threats associated with this, have been ongoing since the term was introduced by McCarthy (1959) in the middle of the last century. These issues certainly deserve attention. In most cases, they remained theoretical views of the problem. However, the situation has changed dramatically over the past year.

That is why we are focusing on the above axiom about the irreversible penetration of AI into our life activities and the subsequent increase in its influence on all spheres. As a consequence of this trend, the need to build a real system of harmonious interaction and relationship between humans and AI becomes obvious.

This problem is likely to be a key issue for this century, as the survival of humanity literally depends on it.

We are not inclined to dramatise the situation about the increasing danger to humanity from the development of AI. We believe that AI, in the absence of individual

consciousness, is not capable of harming humanity. However, the real dangers, which are becoming increasingly apparent, should not be ignored.

In a metaphorical sense, AI can be compared to the fuel or electricity needed to run a machine. The advent of a new fuel (petrol) made it possible for the internal combustion engine to function. Automobiles appeared, aeroplanes... Even today, many people still measure the power of a car's engine in horsepower. Nowadays, hardly anyone has to do their travel planning with horses in mind. But this does not mean that horses have become useless and can be disparaged as unnecessary or inefficient.

It is still directly human beings who decide how to use and interact with new scientific advances. A human can refuel the drone and send it on a research mission to another planet, or send it to destroy the inhabitants of a neighbouring country. A clear example is the Russian Federation's military action in Ukraine. In this case, drones with integrated warheads are actively deployed in large numbers, capable of making a long flight over the battlefield, independently detecting a target, classifying its level of importance among others, and making a decision to destroy it.

Despite the negative trends and realities we live in today, there is still hope that humanity is able to understand the responsibility of using AI and can channel it to advance our civilisation, science and culture.

Therefore, the issue of creating a harmonious relationship between humans and AI is very important. These relationships can be both personal and professional. In this case, personal relationships, such as the role and the level, are determined by each person for him or herself; professional relationships can be regulated from the outside and have serious consequences for the human.

We share the views of researchers who claim that the use of AI will be the reason for the reduction of large numbers of workers in various fields in the coming years. It can cause various social conflicts.

It is therefore crucial to regulate these relationships in a legal and regulatory context.

We think this is difficult to achieve, but it is certainly possible. The challenge is that AI is becoming increasingly pervasive in people's daily lives and workspace. Therefore, something more sophisticated than Asimov's Three Laws of Robotics must be developed to manage this complex system of human-AI relationships (Asimov, 1942).

We believe that in the near future, countries with high levels of economic growth will develop, ratify and implement laws that regulate the norms of interaction and relationships between humans and AI.

Today, thanks to the activities of COPE (2023) and major scientific publishers (WAME, JAMA), standards and rules have been developed for the use of AI-based Chatbots in scientific publications.

The first steps towards legitimising AI-based Chatbots were taken by Melnyk and Pypenko (2022). These scientists have created and implemented the AIC AI Chatbots information technology platform (AIC AI Chatbots, 2023), which provides technological solutions

for the use of AI-based Chatbots (text, images, videos) in scientific research and publications. However, the above standards are voluntary and could be used as a recommended guide. This allows unscrupulous users of AI-based Chatbots to ignore these ethical guidelines. This is why it is necessary to enact laws that regulate the standards of human-AI interaction.

In developing laws and regulations governing standards for human-AI interaction, particular attention should be paid to the protection of human rights in the case of deliberate refusal to use AI.

We believe that human activity without the use of AI will soon have to defend its right to exist. It is a natural human right to freedom of choice and work. Using a special attribution (logo/stamp/label) on a product created by humans without AI involvement can help.

We offer such an attribution “AI Free. Human Created” (Figure 1).

Figure 1

The Attribution “AI Free. Human Created”

The attribution developed enables the classification of products created by humans without the use of AI, as well as increasing the value of natural human labour.

Conclusions

AI has become an integral part of the lives of human beings.

The potential and the speed of development of AI-based information technologies is so great that in the near future humanity may concede primacy to AI.

This situation requires the development, ratification and implementation of laws that regulate the norms of interaction and relationships between humans and AI.

The first steps have already been taken to legitimise AI-based Chatbots in scientific research and publications. This paper offers an attribution for products created by humans without the involvement of AI. The use of the “AI Free. Human Created” attribution helps to protect the individual’s right to freedom of choice and work.

Ethical Approval

The study protocol was consistent with the ethical guidelines of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki as reflected in a prior approval by the Institution’s Human Research Committee.

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